

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D7.1: Regulatory background for smart grid- ready buildings and the energy network

**WP7 – Regulatory framework, project impact,
and go-to-market strategies**

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an EU-level regulatory analysis of the Electricity Market Design (EMD), the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III), the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD recast) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), with a focus on how these frameworks shape the role of buildings in the energy transition. Under their combined implementation, buildings are increasingly expected not only to reduce energy demand, but also to support the decarbonisation of heating, the electrification of end uses, the integration of renewable energy in the built environment, and the gradual phase-out of fossil fuels. In this context, buildings are becoming more important not only as energy consumers, but as active elements of a more flexible, efficient and resilient energy system.

The report examines how the revised EMD, RED III, EPBD and EED together determine whether buildings can contribute to energy sharing, aggregation, smart control, storage, renewable self-consumption and other flexibility services at building and neighbourhood level. In this context, renewable energy generation in buildings and storage are not only relevant measures in their own right, but important enabling conditions for flexibility services, as they increase the ability of buildings to shift demand, optimise self-consumption, interact with dynamic price signals and support the wider integration of renewable electricity. The EMD provides the market framework for active customers, aggregation, dynamic pricing and energy sharing; RED III strengthens collective self-consumption, renewable energy communities and renewable deployment in buildings; the EPBD supports smart-ready, zero-emission and EV-ready buildings, with a particular role for the Smart Readiness Indicator; and the EED reinforces the Energy Efficiency First principle and the need to consider demand-side solutions in planning and investment decisions. Taken together, these provisions determine whether buildings can participate technically, legally and economically in flexibility services at building and neighbourhood level.

The deliverable also reviews implementation lessons from the six BlueBird demo contexts: Spain, Brussels and the Walloon Region in Belgium, Austria, Germany and Poland. The analysis is based on desk research of relevant EU and national legal and policy documents, complemented by structured input from project partners. Across the analysed countries, the report finds that important enabling elements already exist, but their implementation remains uneven and fragmented. In several cases, EU concepts are only partially transposed or not yet operationalised in a way that enables practical uptake. This affects, in particular, the functioning of energy communities, the role of aggregators, the coexistence of multiple contracts, and the ability of buildings to participate effectively in flexibility markets.

At the same time, the report identifies issue-specific enabling practices across the analysed countries rather than one single leading national model. Some countries provide more advanced examples for specific aspects, such as collective self-consumption and multiple-contract arrangements, energy community design, data access, aggregation-related governance, or planning integration. However, the overall picture remains one of partial progress rather than full regulatory readiness. Important barriers include unclear legal definitions, restrictive participation conditions, narrow geographical limits, burdensome administrative procedures, insufficient access to timely and granular metering data from DSOs, and the fact that buildings are still not systematically considered as alternatives to grid reinforcement in network and local planning, despite the direction set by the EED.

Overall, the report shows that the key challenge is not only to introduce relevant legal provisions, but to ensure that they work together in practice. Unlocking the flexibility potential of buildings will require better alignment across directives and national implementation frameworks so that data access, market access, energy sharing, smart-building requirements and system planning function as mutually reinforcing elements. Only under these conditions can buildings support a more decarbonised, efficient, resilient and consumer-centred energy system by integrating distributed renewables, using storage and smart controls to unlock flexibility, reducing system costs and grid pressure, strengthening energy security and competitiveness, and enabling citizens and communities to participate more actively in the energy transition.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CNMC	National Commission on Markets and Competition (Spain)
COEC	Coordination Office for Energy Communities (Austria)
CSC	Collective Self-Consumption
CSIRE	Central Energy Market Information System (Poland)
DSM	Demand-side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	Energy Community
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EE1st	Energy Efficiency First
EEG	Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz / Renewable Energy Sources Act
EMD	Electricity Market Design
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GEG	Gebäudeenergiegesetz / Buildings Energy Act (Germany)
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
NEP	Network Development Plan
NZEB	Nearly Zero-Energy Building
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RED II	Renewable Energy Directive II
RED III	Renewable Energy Directive III
RE	Renewable Energy
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TSO	Transmission System Operator
URE	Energy Regulatory Office (Poland)
VREG	Flemish Regulator of the Electricity and Gas Market
WPG	Wärmeplanungsgesetz / Heat Planning Act (Germany)
ZEB	Zero-Emission Building

I. INTRODUCTION

This report provides an in-depth EU-level regulatory analysis of the Electricity Market Design (EMD), the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III), the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, recast) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), with a focus on how these frameworks shape the role of buildings in the energy transition. Under their combined implementation, buildings are increasingly expected not only to reduce energy demand, but also to support the decarbonisation of heating, the electrification of end uses, the integration of renewable energy in the built environment, and the gradual phase-out of fossil fuels. In this context, buildings are becoming more important not only as energy consumers, but as active elements of a more flexible, efficient and resilient energy system.

At EU level, the revised EMD establishes the core market framework for demand-side flexibility by enabling active customers, aggregation, energy sharing, dynamic electricity pricing and citizen energy communities (CECs). RED III complements this framework by strengthening collective self-consumption (CSC), renewable energy communities (RECs), sector integration and the role of data made available by DSOs. The EED reinforces the Energy Efficiency First principle, extending its application to network planning and system operation and requiring demand-side solutions to be systematically assessed alongside grid investments (Table 1). The EPBD (recast) positions buildings as active energy system assets through requirements on zero-emission buildings (ZEBs), EV-ready infrastructure and, in particular, the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI).

This deliverable also draws on implementation lessons from six demo locations — Spain, Brussels and the Walloon Region in Belgium, Austria, Germany and Poland — based on desk research of relevant EU and national legal and policy documents, complemented by structured input from pilot partners.

For example, in the EMD, Article 15a on energy sharing enables active customers to share renewable electricity and allows an energy-sharing organiser to manage behind-the-meter flexible loads, storage and generation, thereby creating a direct framework for coordinated building-level flexibility. In RED III, Article 20a supports flexibility by requiring DSOs to make relevant aggregated data on demand-response potential and renewable generation available, which is essential for activating and optimising distributed flexibility assets. In the EPBD, Article 15 and Annex IV on the Smart Readiness Indicator explicitly assess a building's ability to adapt to the grid and participate in demand response, load shifting and energy storage. In the EED, Article 3 on the Energy Efficiency First principle requires demand-side resources and system flexibilities to be assessed in planning and major investment decisions, helping ensure that buildings are considered not only as energy consumers, but also as alternatives to grid reinforcement and other supply-side investments.

Table 1 Overview of topics and legal provisions

Topic	Contribution to building flexibility	Legal provision	Directive	Subsection	Differences
Energy sharing legal frameworks	Enables collective investments in renewable energy systems, storage and smart energy management. Possibility to aggregate smaller loads and participate in flexibility markets	Citizen energy community (CEC)	EMD	II.1.	Limited to electricity, legal entity
		Energy sharing and energy sharing organiser	EMD	II.2.	Limited to electricity
		Renewable Energy Community (REC)	REDII	III.1.	Includes electricity and heat, legal entity
		Collective self-consumption (CSC)	REDII	III.2.	Includes electricity and heat, no need for a legal entity
Consider flexibility in planning and investments	If flexibility is considered upfront in energy and network planning, buildings can be treated as alternatives to grid expansion and peaking generation, rather than passive loads	Flexibility as part of Energy Efficiency First principle	EED	V.1.	
		DSOs should consider flexibility	EED	V.1.	
Deployment of renewables in the built environment, urban-level initiatives	Enables local authorities to systematically consider renewable energy communities in strategic decision-making and to actively encourage the deployment of renewable generation, storage, and flexibility assets through accelerated permitting procedures within renewable acceleration area	Renewable acceleration areas	REDIII	III.3.	
		Role of energy communities within heating and cooling plans	EED	V.1.	

II. ELECTRICITY MARKET DESIGN

The Electricity Market Design (EMD) aims to achieve an integrated EU energy market and a cost-effective way to ensure secure, sustainable and affordable energy supply through harmonised energy market rules across EU countries. The following revisions that entered into force on 16 July 2024 set additional goals of boosting renewables and better protecting consumers:

- [DIRECTIVE \(EU\) 2024/1711](#) amending [Directive \(EU\) 2019/944](#) (on common rules for the internal market for electricity)
- [REGULATION \(EU\) 2024/1747](#) amending [Regulation \(EU\) 2019/942](#) (ACER¹) and [Regulation \(EU\) 2019/943](#) (on the internal market for electricity)

This section maps the relevant provisions of the revised EMD and their national implementation in the pilot locations, with a focus on enabling buildings to act as flexible assets. Although the transposition deadline was 17 January 2025, many Member States are lagging behind, not only in implementing the 2024 revisions, but also in fully transposing the original 2019 Directive.

II.1. Citizen energy community

EU-level provisions

<p>Article 2 Definitions Directive (EU) 2019/944</p>	<p>(11) ‘citizen energy community’ means a legal entity that:</p> <p>(a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises;</p> <p>(b) has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits; and</p> <p>(c) may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders;</p>
<p>‘Article 15a Right to energy sharing Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>10.The Commission shall provide guidance to the Member States without increasing the administrative burden in order to facilitate the establishment of a standardised approach with regard to energy sharing and ensure a level playing field for renewable energy communities and citizen energy communities.</p>
<p>Recitals (23) Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>A legal entity that incorporates the criteria of a renewable energy community as defined in Article 2, point (16), of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 or a citizen energy community as defined in Article 2, point (11), of Directive (EU) 2019/944 could share with their members electricity generated from facilities they have in full ownership. The protection and empowerment framework for energy sharing should pay particular attention to vulnerable customers and customers affected by energy poverty.</p>

¹ establishing a European Union Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators

National implementation

For clarity, this report distinguishes between Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) as defined in RED and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) as defined in the electricity market framework, while also considering their practical interaction with collective self-consumption (CSC), since these concepts are related but not identical in scope and regulatory function.

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

Citizen energy communities (CECs) legal frameworks aim to democratize the energy market by establishing legal entities that can generate, store energy, and share with their members the electricity generated. These entities may also be active in aggregation or providing energy services, such as electric vehicle charging or energy efficiency services.

A key advantage for CEC members is the ability to share renewable energy when they can offer a lower price, thereby avoiding the sale of excess generation to the grid, for instance, during periods of peak solar production. Lower prices can occur due lower grid fees for local sharing or simply contract based. In addition, CECs can sell surplus energy back to the grid, which can generate additional revenue and enhance the overall economic viability of the project.

In Spain, CECs would be able to access all organized electricity markets directly (without an aggregator) if the Article 11 of the draft Royal Decree issued by MITECO on 20 April 2023 were approved. They would sell flexibility and other market products directly without the need for an aggregator, as national regulations explicitly grant them access to all organised electricity markets on a non-discriminatory basis. So far this is not the case until the decree is approved, but it has been designed.

In Austria, while CECs may provide energy services including flexibility, they generally operate through aggregators because of licensing and technical constraints, with no explicit right to act independently. However, CECs can apply for the market role “aggregator” and can then act on their own behalf.

In Belgium, both CECs and renewable energy communities (RECs) may engage in aggregation if they obtain the necessary licences, enabling direct market participation subject to administrative requirements.

In contrast, in Germany and Poland, CECs must participate through aggregators, as direct market access remains limited due to complex regulatory and balancing conditions.²

In Austria, CECs must be organised as “an association, cooperative, partnership, corporation, or a similar association with legal personality.” In countries with a strong cooperative tradition, such as Austria and Belgium, this model can further facilitate social acceptance and trust in energy community initiatives.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

The Citizen Energy Community (CEC) framework has so far been only partially implemented, covering general principles but lacking detailed provisions. The regulatory environment remains complex and often requires specialised legal and procedural knowledge, which can hinder the participation of small producers and consumers without access to expert advice. Several Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries are still lagging behind in fully transposing the CEC definition into national legislation (for example, in Poland, the relevant legislative initiative is still under consultation).

Frequent regulatory changes contribute to uncertainty and can impede long-term planning, thereby affecting the stability and overall viability of projects. Furthermore, the establishment and operation of CEC often entail significant administrative, bureaucratic, and transaction costs. These burdens tend

² The rules for energy sharing are defined in Section 42 c of the Energy Industry Act (EnWG).

to increase when regulations are not sufficiently adapted to local contexts, reducing efficiency and raising operational expenditures.

In several Member States, shareholder participation is restricted to natural persons, local authorities, and SMEs. While this limitation aims to prevent corporate capture by large private companies, it also unintentionally excludes large non-profit entities. In Austria, for instance, this restriction poses a barrier for social housing companies and large NGOs seeking to engage in CEC and flexibility projects.

The geographical scope of CECs also varies across countries. In Austria³ and Wallonia⁴, there is no geographical limitation, which may limit the potential for maximising local optimisation and flexibility. Conversely, in Germany⁵, a spatial constraint of 50 km applies, requiring that at least 75% of members natural persons reside within this distance.

Good practice

Austria demonstrates a strong model for citizen energy communities (CECs) by allowing them to provide a wide range of energy services to their members, including energy efficiency measures and electric vehicle charging. This broad functional scope enhances community value and supports local flexibility.

In Brussels, larger companies are permitted to participate in CECs but only in a non-controlling role, ensuring inclusiveness while safeguarding community governance. These practices provide a balance between openness and protection against dominance by large corporate actors.

Policy recommendations

Future regulatory development should build on these examples by harmonising CEC implementation across Member States to enhance legal clarity and market stability.

Policymakers should include detailed provisions on the legal forms of CECs, the conditions for energy sharing and selling, and transparent rules defining membership eligibility. Relevant examples already exist: Austria specifies eligible legal forms and allows a broad range of energy services, Brussels provides clearer governance rules by allowing larger companies only in a non-controlling role, and Spain offers a more enabling framework for market participation and energy sharing.

³ *Electricity Act 2010 (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2010, ElWOG 2010) as amended by Federal Law Gazette I No. 7/2022, Section 16b (Citizen energy communities). Official consolidated English version published by E-Control. This section defines citizen energy communities without introducing a proximity criterion, unlike Section 16c for renewable energy communities.*

https://www.e-control.at/documents/1785851/1811597/ElWOG%2B2010%2C%2BFassung%2Bvom%2B04.03.2022_en.pdf

⁴ *Décret du 12 avril 2001 relatif à l'organisation du marché régional de l'électricité, as amended by the Décret du 5 mai 2022 modifiant diverses dispositions en matière d'énergie dans le cadre de la transposition partielle des directives 2019/944/UE et 2018/2001/UE. See Article 2, 2° sexies (communauté d'énergie citoyenne) and Article 2, 2° quinquies (communauté d'énergies renouvelables). The CEC definition does not include a proximity requirement, whereas the REC definition does.*

https://wallex.wallonie.be/files/pdfs/22/19848_D%C3%A9cret%20relatif%20%C3%A0%20l'organisation%20du%20march%C3%A9%20r%C3%A9gional%20de%20l'electricit%C3%A9%2001-09-2024-13-10-2024.pdf

⁵ *Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG 2023), § 3 Nr. 15 (Bürgerenergiegesellschaft). The provision requires that at least 75% of voting rights are held by natural persons residing in a postcode area located wholly or partly within a 50 km radius of the planned installation. This refers to the German "citizen energy company" framework rather than an explicit CEC transposition.* https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/eeg_2014/_3.html

Measures preventing corporate capture should be maintained, but flexibility should be introduced to allow non-profit or socially oriented large entities, such as social housing organisations, to participate under limited and non-controlling conditions. This approach would support social inclusion, attract investment for community-scale renewable and flexibility projects, and ensure long-term predictability and trust in the CEC framework across the EU.

II.2. Aggregation

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 2 Definitions</i> Directive (EU) 2019/944</p>	<p>(18) ‘aggregation’ means a function performed by a natural or legal person who combines multiple customer loads or generated electricity for sale, purchase or auction in any electricity market;</p>
<p><i>Article 2 Definitions</i> Directive (EU) 2019/944</p>	<p>(19) ‘independent aggregator’ means a market participant engaged in aggregation who is not affiliated to the customer’s supplier;</p>

National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

A clear and legally defined concept of an aggregator is essential to enable buildings to act as flexibility assets. A well-defined legal framework ensures that aggregators can operate transparently, coordinate effectively with grid operators and suppliers, and provide fair access to flexibility markets. This legal clarity is crucial to unlock the flexibility potential of buildings, attract investment, and integrate them efficiently into the wider energy system.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Although all Member States refer to the EU definition of an aggregator, national transpositions show notable differences in scope and clarity. In Spain, aggregation activities are recognised in legislation but lack a detailed legal and operational framework, creating administrative and licensing challenges and costs. Poland has a basic legal definition of an aggregator, but the framework for independent aggregators remains limited and costly to implement. Germany’s approach is more advanced, allowing both natural and legal persons to operate as aggregators under a well-defined and functioning system. In Brussels and Austria, citizen energy communities may act as aggregators if they obtain the necessary licences and meet technical standards, yet administrative processes are still largely manual and cumbersome.

Good practice

Brussels Region

"CEC and REC may carry out aggregation activities, provided they obtain the necessary licenses and comply with the legal obligations associated with this activity, including financial guarantees and technical expertise."

[Loi sur les marchés de l'électricité, 15 MARS 2021, Section 15\(4\)](#)

Policy recommendations

Member States should establish clear and harmonised rules for the licensing and registration of aggregators, as well as transparent settlement and data exchange procedures between aggregators, suppliers, and distribution system operators (DSOs).

Regulatory frameworks should also include standardised mechanisms for coordination and fair compensation between aggregators and balance responsible parties. These measures would reduce administrative complexity, enhance market transparency, and enable the effective activation of flexibility services across the EU.

Following the example of Austria, Germany and Brussels, CEC and prosumers should be allowed to directly offer aggregation services, as this would enhance the business case for flexibility assets. Introducing intermediary entities as mandatory aggregators weakens this business case by increasing transaction costs and reducing the economic value retained by local participants.

II.3. Energy sharing and energy sharing organiser

EU-level provisions

<p>Article 2 Definitions Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>“energy sharing” means the self-consumption by active customers of renewable energy either:</p> <p>(a) generated or stored offsite or on sites between them by a facility they own, lease or rent in whole or in part;</p>
<p>Article 15a Right to energy sharing Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>1. Member States shall ensure that all households, small enterprises and medium-sized enterprises, public bodies and, where a Member State has so decided, other categories of final customer have the right to participate in energy sharing as active customers in a non-discriminatory manner, within the same bidding zone or a more limited geographical area, as determined by that Member State.</p> <p>2. Member States shall ensure that active customers are entitled to share renewable energy between themselves based on private agreements or through a legal entity. Participation in energy sharing shall not constitute the primary commercial or professional activity of active customers engaged in energy sharing.</p>
<p>Article 15a Right to energy sharing Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>3. Active customers may appoint a third party as an energy sharing organiser for the purposes of:</p> <p>(a) communicating about the energy sharing arrangements with other relevant entities, such as suppliers and network operators, including on aspects related to the applicable tariffs and charges, taxes or levies;</p> <p>(b) providing support for managing and balancing behind-the-meter flexible loads, distributed renewable energy generation and storage facilities that are part of the relevant energy sharing arrangement;</p> <p>(c) contracting and billing active customers that participate in energy sharing;</p>

	(d) installation and operation, including metering and maintenance, of the renewable energy generation or storage facility.
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

Several aspects of the energy-sharing provisions act as drivers for collective investment in renewables, storage, and flexibility assets. Energy sharing enables households, SMEs and public bodies to jointly use locally generated renewable electricity and distribute the benefits among participants. By allowing this through private agreements, legal entities or an energy-sharing organiser, the framework lowers organisational barriers and makes it easier to coordinate storage, behind-the-meter loads and local renewable generation for flexibility purposes.

The energy sharing organiser is responsible for setting up sharing contracts and agreements between small-scale prosumers and suppliers or network operators, handling billing, and managing behind-the-meter loads.

The Brussels region has overall implemented the role of the energy-sharing organiser in a robust way and closely aligned with the EMD provisions. However, the connection to the data hub is still handled manually, which creates inefficiencies and limits the full automation of the process.

Good practice

Spain provides an enabling framework for energy sharing by allowing participants to share renewable electricity without creating a legal entity across a significantly wider geographical range. Standard shared self-consumption is permitted when generation and consumption points are connected at low voltage and located within 500 meters, measured by the orthogonal projection of the metering equipment. This distance is extended **up to 2,000 meters for PV installations** placed entirely on rooftops, industrial land, or other artificial structures connected to consumers through distribution lines. This approach lowers administrative burdens, widens participation beyond single buildings, and facilitates neighbourhood-scale collective PV projects, making it a good practice for enabling energy sharing.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

In Spain and Walloon Region, a significant barrier to effective energy sharing stems from the fact that **only the DSO has first-hand access to metering data**, preventing energy-sharing organisers, aggregators, and smaller collective prosumers from accessing the information required to verify shared energy volumes or participate in flexibility markets.

In Poland, the barrier takes a different form: **high administrative fees** and costs linked to registering and operating as an energy-sharing organiser or aggregator make participation unattractive or financially unviable for smaller actors. These fees add to already complex administrative procedures, creating high transaction costs that discourage households, SMEs, and emerging energy communities from entering energy-sharing schemes.

An additional barrier is the lack of simple and standardised procedures for setting up and operating energy-sharing arrangements. Where participation requires complex contracts, multiple

intermediaries, manual data exchange or burdensome registration steps, energy sharing becomes too difficult and costly for households, SMEs and smaller communities, even where the legal possibility formally exists.

Combined, these barriers limit the scalability of energy sharing, hinder the activation of local flexibility, and prevent decentralised renewable resources from fully contributing to system optimisation.

Policy recommendations

A more enabling framework for energy sharing should remove unnecessary middlemen and the additional transaction costs they create, allowing participants to enter into direct private agreements alongside the use of legal entities or energy-sharing organisers. To make energy sharing accessible to a wider group of households, SMEs and public bodies, the scope should be expanded beyond single buildings. This can be achieved by permitting energy sharing without a legal entity across larger geographic areas, for example within the same LV/MV grid or within a clearly defined distance threshold such as 2 km, following the Spanish model, provided that technical conditions, metering arrangements and DSO coordination are properly ensured. Such an approach reduces administrative burdens and strengthens the economic case for collective self-consumption and flexibility services.

II.4. Choice of supplier and types of contracts

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 4</i></p> <p>Free choice of supplier</p> <p>Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>Member States shall ensure that all customers are free to purchase electricity from suppliers of their choice. Member States shall ensure that all customers are free to have more than one electricity supply contract or energy sharing agreement at the same time, and that, for that purpose, customers are entitled to have more than one metering and billing point covered by the single connection point for their premises. Where technically feasible, smart metering systems deployed in accordance with Article 19 may be used to allow customers to have more than one electricity supply contract or more than one energy sharing agreement at the same time.';</p>
<p><i>Article 11</i></p> <p>Entitlement to a dynamic electricity price contract</p> <p>Directive (EU) 2024/1711</p>	<p>Member States shall ensure that the national regulatory framework enables suppliers to offer fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contracts and dynamic electricity price contracts. Member States shall ensure that final customers who have a smart meter installed can request to conclude a dynamic electricity price contract and that all final customers can request to conclude a fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contract with a duration of at least one year, with at least one supplier and with every supplier that has more than 200,000 final customers.</p> <p>By way of derogation from the first subparagraph, Member States may exempt a supplier with more than 200,000 final customers from the obligation to offer fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contracts, where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the supplier offers only dynamic price contracts; (b) the exemption does not have a negative impact on competition; and (c) there remains a sufficient choice of fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contracts for final customers.

<p>Article 5</p> <p>Market-based supply prices</p> <p>Directive (EU) 2019/944</p>	<p>1. Suppliers shall be free to determine the price at which they supply electricity to customers. Member States shall take appropriate actions to ensure effective competition between suppliers.</p> <p>3.... Member States may apply public interventions in the price setting for the supply of electricity to energy poor or vulnerable household customers.</p> <p>6. For the purpose of a transition period to establish effective competition for electricity supply contracts between suppliers, and to achieve fully effective market-based retail pricing of electricity in accordance with paragraph 1, Member States may apply public interventions in the price setting for the supply of electricity to household customers and to microenterprises that do not benefit from public interventions pursuant to paragraph 3.</p>
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National implementation

Spain now provides a better and more up-to-date example for **Article 4**, while Austria and Wallonia remain examples for **Article 11**.

In Spain, Real Decreto 88/2026 provides a concrete example of the implementation of Article 4 on free choice of supplier. It explicitly allows consumers, where consumption is properly metered, to hold more than one electricity supply contract simultaneously at the same supply point and confirms access to several contracts with several suppliers. It also enables direct participation in electricity markets and direct bilateral procurement with a producer. This creates a clearer framework for combining self-consumption or energy-sharing arrangements with a separate supplier contract for the remaining electricity demand. With this Spain addresses multiple contracts + direct market/bilateral participation.

In Austria, energy suppliers serving more than 50,000 metering points are obliged to offer dynamic price contracts. In Wallonia, a **dynamic price contract** is defined as “an electricity supply contract concluded between a supplier and an end customer **that reflects price variations on the spot markets, including the day-ahead and intraday markets, at intervals at least equivalent to the imbalance settlement frequency.**” Dynamic price contracts can enable customers to both support the electricity system and reduce their overall electricity costs, even without any change in consumption volume⁶. These two benefits are significant but can only be realised if consumers have access to smart meters and installed flexibility assets. These solutions address dynamic and fixed contract implementation.

For those unable to benefit from such smart controls, the EMD also provides the possibility for final customers to request a **fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contract**. Vulnerable households may fall under this category, and Article 5, therefore, enables Member States to **apply public interventions in price setting for the supply of electricity to energy-poor or vulnerable household customers**. According to the EMD, suppliers with more than 200,000 final customers should offer both dynamic price contracts and fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contracts, although exceptions may apply.

⁶ <https://smarten.eu/reports/implementing-eu-laws-a-guide-to-activate-demand-side-flexibility-in-the-eu-27-member-states-2/>

Policy recommendations

While most Member States have implemented provisions ensuring the free choice of energy supplier, this market-design principle can unintentionally hinder the development of energy-sharing agreements, including collective self-consumption (CSC), RECs or integrated local energy-management schemes.

Free choice of supplier only becomes a barrier where national rules do not properly enable its practical coexistence with energy-sharing arrangements, for example by still assuming a single supplier, single metering structure or single billing relationship per connection point.

To address this barrier, Article 4 of the Electricity Market Design **explicitly allows customers to hold multiple electricity supply contracts or participate simultaneously in energy-sharing arrangements**. In Spain, this has been operationalised by enabling consumers to maintain one contract covering the portion of their demand supplied through CSCs or a REC, while freely choosing a supplier for the remaining grid-supplied electricity. This could be an example to follow by other member states. This approach provides a practical model that could be replicated by other Member States.

Regarding dynamic electricity price contracts and fixed-term, fixed-price electricity supply contracts, Member States should ensure that this choice of contracts is effectively implemented, in particular for large suppliers serving more than 200 000 final customers. The availability of **dynamic electricity price contracts enables households to benefit from investments in flexibility assets**, such as smart HVAC systems or smart appliance controls. At the same time, **Member States should consider tailored measures for vulnerable households, including public interventions in price setting for energy-poor or vulnerable customers** (Article 5), or support measures such as **access to deep renovations and participation in energy sharing agreements, or REC membership**.

Member States should not only ensure the formal availability of dynamic electricity price contracts, but also their visibility and comparability through clear supplier information, standardised contract presentation and easy-to-use comparison tools, so that consumers can actually identify and choose suitable offers.

III. RENEWABLE ENERGY DIRECTIVE

The revised Renewable Energy Directive (REDIII), [Directive \(EU\) 2023/2413](#), entered into force on 20 November 2023. It sets an overall binding target of at least 42.5% renewable energy at the EU level by 2030, with a specific renewable energy benchmark of 49% for energy consumption in buildings. The REDIII supports buildings as flexible assets by requiring Member States to promote smart, renewable-based electrification and to increase the renewable energy used in buildings, including through collective self-consumption, RECs, local energy storage, and demand-response services. The revisions include important provisions introducing faster permitting procedures for small installations and RECs, as well as within renewable acceleration areas, and establishing new obligations for DSOs to make relevant aggregated data available.

III.1. Renewable Energy Community

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 2 Definitions</i></p>	<p>(16) ‘renewable energy community’ means a legal entity:</p> <p>(a) which, in accordance with the applicable national law, is based on open and voluntary participation, is autonomous, and is effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity;</p> <p>(b) the shareholders or members of which are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities;</p> <p>(c) the primary purpose of which is to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits;</p>
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) can enable collective investments in renewable energy generation, energy storage and smart energy management systems, thereby strengthening building flexibility through increased local production, coordination and more efficient use of flexible assets. **In Austria, this potential is supported by a legal framework, Elektrizitätswirtschaftsgesetz ElWG⁷, that allows RECs to organise collective energy use within a defined geographical proximity, linked to the local or regional grid area.** By pooling flexible assets across multiple buildings, such as heat pumps, electric vehicles, batteries and controllable loads, RECs can support load shifting, self-

⁷ https://ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2025_I_91/BGBLA_2025_I_91.html;
https://www.e-netze.at/downloads-data/pdf.aspx?pdf=ElWG_Fassung+vom+07012026.pdf;

NOTE that the Bürgerenergie sections §§ 66–72 of the new ElWG enter into force on **1 October 2026** under § 188 Abs. 3., The new ElWG is already largely in force, but the sources are clear that the established forms of energy communities are retained and that the energy-community regime will be integrated into the new shared-energy-use system only from 1 October 2026. They also explicitly note that benefits for RECs can already be claimed under existing law (ElWOG 2010).

https://360.lexisnexis.at/d/rechtsnorm-ris/66_elwg/L-20013066-P66-ZF1

consumption, storage dispatch and participation in flexibility services at building and neighbourhood level.

Good practice

Austria

EIWG §6 Z 45: “REC means a legal entity that enables to jointly utilise the energy generated within the community; its members or shareholders must be located **in the nearby area**, as defined in § 70 Abs. 6 Z 3 or 4 ”

EIWOG §16c (2): “Within a REC, the consumption points of the members or shareholders must be connected to the generation points via a **low-voltage distribution grid and the low-voltage section of the transformer station** (local area) or via the medium-voltage grid and the **medium-voltage busbar in the transformer station** (regional area) in the concession area of a grid operator.”

Austria remains a relevant example of a clear REC framework. At present, RECs continue to operate under the existing EAG/EIWOG regime, including the established proximity logic linking participation to the local or regional grid area. Under the new EIWG, this core logic is retained, but from 1 October 2026 RECs will be integrated into a broader framework for active customers and shared energy use. This suggests continuity rather than a reversal, while also expanding the organisational possibilities for decentralised energy use.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Most Member States have implemented the definition in a manner largely aligned with RED II; however, in many cases, the definition was transposed without sufficient detail to enable the effective establishment and operation of RECs in practice.

In **Poland**, the concept of an energy cooperative is framed around cooperative entities whose purpose is the production of electricity, biogas, agricultural biogas, biomethane, or heat from renewable energy installations, as well as the trading or storage of these energy carriers as part of their activities⁸.

In **Austria**, a key barrier under the current REC framework is the exclusion of large enterprises from participation in renewable energy communities. Under EAG § 79(2), REC members or general partners may be natural persons, municipalities, other public-law legal persons, or SMEs. This approach is particularly problematic in the Austrian context, where social housing companies have a long-standing tradition. Although these entities qualify as large enterprises, they primarily provide housing to vulnerable and low-income households. Excluding such actors from RECs therefore indirectly excludes significant segments of the vulnerable population, which runs counter to EU

⁸ Article 1 § 1 of the Law of September 16, 1982. - Cooperative Law (Journal of Laws of 2021, item 648 and of 2023, item 1450)

objectives that emphasise the support and inclusion of vulnerable customers through energy communities.

At the same time, Austria’s framework gives RECs a potentially strong role in flexibility provision. Under EAG § 79(1), RECs may produce, consume, store and sell renewable energy, act as aggregators, and provide other energy services. In legal terms, this means that RECs can in principle participate directly in flexibility-related activities. In practice, however, it is considerably more likely that a REC will provide flexibility services through an aggregator, given the complexity of market participation and the associated administrative and technical burdens.

Policy recommendations

- **Broaden eligibility rules where these unnecessarily restrict participation.**
Member States should ensure that REC frameworks do not exclude socially relevant actors, such as social housing providers or other mission-driven entities, where this would indirectly prevent vulnerable households from benefiting from community-based renewable energy and flexibility solutions.
- **Align the different energy community frameworks.**
Within the discretion available under national transposition, policymakers should seek to minimise unnecessary inconsistencies between different community frameworks and ensure that communities can combine renewable energy sharing, storage and flexibility services as smoothly as possible.

Further guidance at EU level on the practical interaction between Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and collective self-consumption (CSC) could help reduce fragmentation and support integrated local energy and flexibility models.

This would also be consistent with the European Commission’s Citizen Energy Package, which refers more broadly to “energy communities” and foresees further guidance for Member States, practical support measures and future interoperability rules for easier energy sharing.

III.2. Collective self-consumption

EU-level provisions

Article 2 Definitions	(15) ‘jointly acting renewables self consumers’ means a group of at least two jointly acting renewables self consumers in accordance with point (14) who are located in the same building or multi-apartment block
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

Collective self-consumption (CSC) can contribute to making buildings flexible assets by enabling collective investments in renewable energy systems, energy storage and integrated energy management. CSC can be implemented either within a single building, covering energy demand of common areas and/or of individual dwellings; or, where regulation allows, between several buildings within a defined geographical range. On their own, individual dwellings usually offer only limited flexibility; however, CSC makes aggregation possible.

By sharing locally generated renewable electricity, CSC can improve self-consumption rates and reduce reliance on the grid, which may provide some economic incentive to invest in flexible technologies such as smart heating systems, shared storage or energy management solutions.

However, the extent to which these incentives materialise depends strongly on national regulatory frameworks, tariff structures and access to markets for flexibility services.

Compared to REC or CEC, CSC is generally simpler to implement, as it does not necessarily require the establishment of a legal entity. This can lower administrative and organisational barriers, particularly in residential and social housing contexts. Nevertheless, simplified governance alone does not guarantee effective flexibility activation without appropriate technical standards and market access.

Good practice

Spain – collective self-consumption⁹

Spain provides a comparatively clear regulatory framework for collective self-consumption, enabling several consumers to share electricity from a nearby generation installation. A key strength is that the framework defines multiple proximity criteria under which generation and consumption facilities can be considered associated, which increases practical applicability in different local contexts. In addition, electricity can be allocated among participating consumers through agreed distribution coefficients, offering flexibility in how shared generation is organised. Overall, the Spanish framework provides legal clarity and operational options that can support the uptake of collective self-consumption models.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

A key barrier to the deployment of CSC and the provision of flexibility services lies in the restrictive geographical and technical conditions under which such schemes are implemented in many Member States. In several countries, collective self-consumption remains largely confined to a single building or a multi-apartment block, reflecting the minimum scope allowed under RED II.

In **Wallonia** and **Brussels**, CSC is permitted for active energy prosumers located within the same building and connected to the local grid, subject to the installation of smart meters and settlement based on 15-minute imbalances. While this framework enables basic forms of energy sharing, it remains limited in scale and does not support more complex configurations that could unlock higher flexibility potential at the neighbourhood level.

The **Austrian** legal framework illustrates how these constraints can become a structural barrier in practice. Austria follows a particularly restrictive approach, requiring that participating consumers and generation units be connected through the same communal line and located in proximity, explicitly prohibiting the use of the public grid¹⁰. As a result, CSC schemes can only be implemented where all participants share the same grid connection point. This requirement poses a significant obstacle for larger housing developments or housing estates, such as those developed by social housing providers, where buildings are often connected through multiple grid connection points rather than a single communal line. Even where buildings are located in immediate physical proximity, the lack of a shared connection infrastructure can make collective self-consumption legally or technically impossible, thereby limiting the scalability of such schemes and constraining their contribution to flexibility services and local system optimisation.

⁹ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2019-5089>

¹⁰ §16a(2) of the [Electricity Industry and Organisation Act \(EIWOG\)](#)

By contrast, Spain has adopted a more enabling framework, extending collective self-consumption beyond a single building and allowing participation within a radius of up to two kilometres.

Policy recommendations

There is a persistent **market and regulatory confusion between collective self-consumption (CSC), citizen energy communities (CEC) and renewable energy communities (REC)**. Because CSC, CECs and RECs serve different but complementary functions, it is important that national frameworks distinguish them clearly in practice. In particular, CSC should remain a simple entry point for collective renewable use in apartment buildings, small collectives and social housing settings, rather than being constrained by rules that unnecessarily push projects towards more complex legal forms.

Note: Because CSC, CECs and RECs are often confused in practice, Table 1 in the introduction highlights their main legal differences: CECs are electricity-based legal entities under the EMD, RECs are broader community entities under RED, and CSC provides a simpler framework for collective renewable self-consumption without necessarily requiring a legal entity.

In this context, CSC has a particularly important but underused role. In theory, CSC can enable energy sharing, collective renewable energy production, as well as shared energy storage and coordinated energy management among participants. **Compared to CECs and RECs, CSC offers a simpler entry point, as it does not require the establishment of a legal entity.** This significantly lowers administrative and organisational barriers and makes CSC especially suitable for apartment buildings, small collectives and social housing settings.

However, in many Member States, **the potential of CSC is constrained by restrictive interpretations of proximity and grid use.** Limiting CSC strictly to a single building block, or requiring participation only where a common grid connection exists, reduces its ability to scale up and limits its contribution to flexibility services. These restrictions hinder replication in dense urban areas and in social housing contexts, where buildings are often physically close but connected through different grid connection points.

Overall, such limitations reduce the potential of CSC to act as a driver for demand-side flexibility and undermine broader objectives related to the integration of distributed renewable generation and local flexibility. Member States could address this barrier by allowing CSC beyond the single-building level, for example within a defined geographical radius. **The Spanish approach, which permits CSC within a radius of up to two kilometres, provides a practical model that could be replicated** to enable wider participation while maintaining a local character.

III.3. Renewable acceleration areas

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 15c Renewables acceleration areas</i></p>	<p>1 By 27 months after the entry into force, Member States shall ensure that competent authorities adopt a plan or plans designating, as a subset of the areas referred to in Article 15b(1), renewables acceleration areas for one or more types of renewable energy sources.</p> <p>(i) give priority to artificial and built surfaces, such as rooftops and facades of buildings, transport infrastructure and their direct surroundings, parking areas, farms, waste sites, industrial sites, mines, artificial inland water bodies, lakes or reservoirs, and, where appropriate, urban waste water treatment sites, as well as degraded land not usable for agriculture;</p>
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

The revised RED III introduces the obligation for Member States to designate Renewable Acceleration Areas to streamline permitting procedures for renewable energy projects. As the Directive entered into force in November 2023, the 27-month transposition and implementation deadline falls in February 2026. At this stage, it is therefore still too early to comprehensively assess the full implementation and effectiveness of this provision across Member States.

Preliminary developments nevertheless indicate heterogeneous progress. **Germany** has implemented the specifications for designating acceleration areas for onshore wind and solar energy through amendments to the Federal Building Code (Baugesetzbuch BauGB)¹¹ and the Spatial Planning Act (Raumordnungsgesetz ROG). These changes also enable higher-level planning frameworks to designate areas for solar energy installations and associated energy storage systems as acceleration areas.

In **Austria**, implementation is partial. While some regions have taken initial steps towards designating suitable areas, the federal Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz (Renewable Expansion Act) remains pending, limiting nationwide consistency. In **Wallonia**, steps towards implementation have been initiated, indicating alignment with the Directive's objectives¹², although a full assessment will only be possible closer to the transposition deadline.

Policy recommendations

This provision is important for making buildings flexible assets because it steers renewable energy development towards the **built environment**, where flexibility can be effectively activated and used by the energy system. Prioritising rooftops and façades means that renewable generation is directly connected to on-site consumption, storage, EV charging and building management systems. **This proximity allows electricity to be shifted in time, stored or self-consumed, instead of being injected passively into the grid.**

Developing renewables on buildings is therefore more conducive to flexibility than placing them on agricultural land, where generation is typically remote from demand and mainly contributes to grid injections. In contrast, building-integrated renewables support demand response, local balancing and aggregation across multiple buildings, reducing peak loads and grid congestion.

In renewables acceleration areas, **faster permitting reduces project risk and shortens payback times**, which encourages investment not only in generation but also in complementary flexibility technologies such as storage and smart energy management. This makes timely implementation by cities and regions essential to unlock the flexibility potential of buildings and ensure timely system benefits.

¹¹

<https://www.bundeswirtschaftsministerium.de/Redaktion/DE/Artikel/Service/Gesetzesvorhaben/240403-gesetz-umsetzung-red-3-wind-an-land-und-solarenergie.html>

¹² Décret du 29 avril 2024 <https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/loi-decret/2024/04/29/2024204576>

III.4. Data availability by DSOs

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 20a</i></p> <p><i>Facilitating System integration of renewable electricity</i></p>	<p>If technically available, distribution system operators shall also make available anonymised and aggregated data on the demand response potential and the renewable electricity generated and injected to the grid by self-consumers and renewable energy communities.</p>
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

DSO data provision as an enabler for energy sharing and flexibility, With regard to energy sharing in Renewable Energy Communities in **Austria**, ElWOG §16e(1)²¹³¹⁴ requires **DSOs** to **make** measured **quarter-hourly generation and consumption data** of participating grid users **available** to suppliers and the energy community without delay and at the latest on the following day, in line with market rules. This obligation is a key enabler for energy sharing, as it allows accurate allocation of shared energy, settlement of volumes and the activation of behind-the-meter flexibility based on near-real-time data.

Austria adopted the new **Elektrizitätswirtschaftsgesetz (ElWOG)** in December 2025, replacing ElWOG. For energy communities, however, the core enabling logic remains broadly continuous: the established REC and CEC models are retained and will be integrated into the new shared-energy-use system from **1 October 2026**.

Details of the changes: In Austria, metering and data exchange for energy sharing are a key enabler for both RECs and CECs and regulated in the same paragraph. Under the previous framework, **ElWOG 2010 § 16e Abs. 1 Z 2** required DSOs to provide measured quarter-hourly generation and consumption data to suppliers and participating energy communities, with additional cross-operator exchange rules in **§ 16e Abs. 2**. In the new ElWOG, this logic is carried forward in **§ 71 Abs. 1 Z 2** and **Abs. 2**. The new common framework in **§§ 66–72 ElWOG** will apply from **1 October 2026**. The new ElWOG appears to strengthen the approach by moving toward a more data-centric framework in which quarter-hourly smart-meter data become the standard basis for market processes.

In **Poland**, recent regulatory developments also point towards increased data transparency and access to support demand-side response and flexibility services, notably through the Central Information System of the Energy Market (CSIRE). By improving access to metering and consumption data, CSIRE is expected to facilitate more efficient exchange of information between market participants and support the development of targeted demand-side response and flexibility services. For aggregators, suppliers and energy service companies, access to anonymised and aggregated consumption data and

¹³

<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20007045>

Republic of Austria. *Electricity Act 2010 (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2010, ElWOG 2010)*, as amended by Federal Law Gazette I No. 7/2022, **Section 16b** (Citizen energy communities). Official consolidated English version published by E-Control. This section defines citizen energy communities without introducing a proximity criterion, unlike Section 16c for renewable energy communities.

¹⁴ **Old:** ElWOG 2010 § 16e Abs. 1 Z 2, Abs. 2

New: ElWOG § 71 Abs. 1 Z 2, Abs. 2 comes into act starting 1.October 2026

load profiles can improve the design of service offerings. For DSOs and TSOs, improved data availability can support congestion management, system balancing and more efficient network operation, potentially reducing the need for costly grid reinforcement and helping integrate flexible resources.

Spain – Datadis as an enabling data-access instrument. Spain has developed an important practical instrument for electricity data access through **Datadis**¹⁵, which provides an important practical instrument for access to electricity data, including hourly consumption data for individual consumers, as well as anonymised and aggregated data; consumers can also authorise third parties to access their data. Datadis also includes generation data and self-consumption surpluses. In addition, the **SIPS**¹⁶ system contains technical, consumption and commercial data on supply points, and recent regulation further strengthens free consumer access to supply-point databases through digital means. Together with recent rules requiring free telematic access to supply-point databases, this provides a comparatively strong basis for improving data availability for demand-side participation and flexibility services.

Good practice

Austria – DSO data provision as an enabler for energy communities and flexibility

Austria provides a strong example of how clear data-access obligations can enable collective energy action and flexibility. Under the existing framework, DSOs must measure the consumption and feed-in of energy community members and make **quarter-hourly data** available to suppliers and the energy community **on the following day**, free of charge and online. This is a particularly relevant good practice because it turns data exchange into an operational right rather than a vague principle. In practice, such near-real-time access supports accurate energy sharing, settlement, and the activation of flexibility options within RECs and CECs. The newer EIWG appears to continue and further systematise this data-centric approach, suggesting regulatory continuity rather than disruption.

Spain – Datadis and strengthened access to supply-point data.

Spain offers a good practice example through the combination of an operational data-access platform and a stronger legal basis for data availability. Datadis already supports consumer and authorised third-party access to detailed electricity data, while the 2026 supply, commercialisation and aggregation regulation requires distributors to maintain complete and updated supply-point databases, guarantee **free telematic access**, and allow **suppliers and independent aggregators** to access and process these data without additional access conditions. Consumers must also be able to access their own data free of charge, while confidentiality protections are preserved. This creates a comparatively strong framework for improving transparency, facilitating market entry, and supporting more targeted flexibility and demand-side service development, even if practical limitations may still remain.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

In **Austria**, a key barrier to effective data sharing by DSOs is the delayed availability of metering data. Although quarter-hourly data are made available to energy communities and suppliers, access is typically only provided on the following day. This delay significantly limits the integration of battery storage within energy communities, as real-time or near-real-time data are required for optimal

¹⁵ <https://datadis.es/home>

¹⁶ <https://www.cnmc.es/sectores-que-regulamos/energia/sips>

charging and discharging decisions. Without timely data access, energy communities must rely on additional, often costly, technical equipment to operate storage assets efficiently, increasing complexity and transaction costs.

In **Poland**, DSOs will be required to share anonymised data through the Central Energy Market Information System (CSIRE), which is intended to support services such as demand-side response. However, CSIRE is operational, but its full functionality is expected to be achieved in the second half of 2026. Additional challenges include data quality and standardisation issues stemming from legacy DSO IT systems, constraints linked to data privacy and GDPR compliance that limit data granularity, and high implementation costs for secure data collection and anonymisation. These barriers are compounded by the still limited maturity of the flexibility market, which reduces the immediate ability of market actors to fully exploit shared data. The Polish TSO - PSE is responsible for the management and operation of the CSIRE portal in Poland.

In **Brussels**, insufficient data transparency and restricted access to metering and system data similarly hinder the development of flexibility services and the efficient use of distributed storage and demand response.

In **Spain**, despite good progress, a few practical and regulatory limitations remain. Existing systems do not yet amount to a fully developed flexibility-oriented data framework for all relevant actors, and access conditions, scope, and timeliness still limit the effective use of data by energy communities, aggregators and energy managers. In particular, access to SIPS data remains regulated and restricted to defined user categories.

Policy recommendations

Member States should ensure the full and timely implementation of Article 20a of the REDIII by establishing clear and enforceable obligations for DSOs to provide the data necessary for system integration and flexibility services. DSOs should provide access to metering and system data in near-real time, or as close to real time as technically feasible, rather than with systematic delays. Next-day data availability, while an improvement over ex-post reporting, is insufficient to unlock the full flexibility potential of buildings, particularly for battery storage, electric vehicles and other fast-reacting assets that require timely information for optimal operation. Regulatory frameworks should therefore progressively move from next-day to intraday or real-time data access standards.

National regulatory authorities should ensure that data access is granted on a non-discriminatory basis to self-consumers, energy communities, aggregators and energy managers, under transparent conditions and standardised formats. This includes harmonised data models, interfaces and protocols to avoid fragmentation across DSOs and to reduce transaction costs for smaller actors in the flexibility market.

IV. ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS DIRECTIVE

The recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), [Directive \(EU\) 2024/1275](#), is the key legislative instrument for decarbonising the EU building stock. It introduces measures to accelerate the renovation rate, improve energy performance, boost the uptake of renewables in buildings, and reduce embodied greenhouse gas emissions.

The EPBD recast strengthens the role of buildings as active elements of the energy system. It promotes the deployment of technical building systems capable of responding to external signals, encourages the integration of renewable energy and on-site storage, and supports the roll-out of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles. Through the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), the EPBD introduces requirements and incentives for buildings to become “flexibility-ready”, meaning they can adjust consumption, store energy, or provide demand response. This significantly enhances the ability of building-level assets, such as heat pumps, batteries, EV chargers, and smart controls, to participate in energy sharing arrangements and contribute to system-wide flexibility services.

IV.1. Smart readiness indicator

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Recital 56</i> Directive (EU) 2024/1275</p>	<p>The smart readiness indicator should be used to measure the capacity of buildings to use information and communication technologies and electronic systems to adapt the operation of buildings to the needs of the occupants and the grid and to improve the energy efficiency and overall performance of buildings. The smart readiness indicator should raise awareness among building owners and occupants of the value behind building automation and electronic monitoring of technical building systems and should give confidence to occupants about the actual savings of those new enhanced-functionalities. The smart readiness indicator is particularly beneficial for large buildings with a high energy demand. For other buildings, the scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings should be optional for Member States.</p>
<p><i>Article 15 Smart readiness of buildings</i> Directive (EU) 2024/1275</p>	<p>1) ... The rating shall be based on an assessment of the capabilities of a building or building unit to adapt its operation to the needs of the occupant, in particular concerning indoor environmental quality and the grid and to improve its energy efficiency and overall performance.</p> <p>2) ... requiring the application of the common Union scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings, in accordance with Annex IV, to non-residential buildings with an effective rated output for <i>heating systems, air-conditioning systems, systems for combined space heating and ventilation, or systems for combined air-conditioning and ventilation</i> of over 290 kW.</p>
<p><i>ANNEX IV Common general framework for rating the smart readiness of buildings</i></p>	<p>2(c) the flexibility of a building’s overall energy demand, including its ability to enable participation in active and passive as well as implicit and explicit demand response, through its energy storage and release of energy back to the</p>

<u>Directive (EU) 2024/1275</u>	grid, for example through flexibility and load shifting capacities;
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National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

Methodological testing and alignment with national frameworks

A key driver for SRI implementation is the use of official test phases to benchmark the SRI methodology against existing national approaches, particularly those addressing energy flexibility and smart building assessment. This driver is clearly present in **Austria**, where the test phase¹⁷ explicitly compares SRI outcomes with national flexibility assessment methods using detailed case studies across various building types. This approach supports regulatory learning and reduces the risk of duplication by clarifying how the SRI complements established national instruments.

Integration of energy flexibility and smart readiness objectives

The positioning of the SRI as a tool contributing to broader energy system flexibility and smart readiness objectives acts as an enabling driver. This is evident in **Austria** (*residential and non-residential cases*), where flexibility benchmarking is a core element of the pilot, and in **Germany**, where methodological adaptation focuses on national building stock characteristics relevant to digitalisation and smart operation. In **Spain** (*primarily non-residential*), the developed tool includes 3 pillars: energy efficiency (envelop and systems), users interactions, and flexibility. In all cases, the SRI is framed as part of the wider energy transition rather than a standalone indicator.

Development of digital tools and assessment infrastructure

Investment in digital infrastructure and assessment tools supports scalability and consistency of SRI implementation. This driver is visible in **Austria** through active tool development accompanying the pilot phase¹⁸, and in **Germany**, where the test phase includes a digital infrastructure for the simple calculation of the SRI¹⁹ and in Spain where the project SRI2MARKET has developed a tool to assess the indicator. These efforts address operational feasibility and reduce long-term administrative burden.

Assessor training and capacity building

The availability of trained assessors and dedicated guidance is a critical driver for operationalising the SRI. This driver is strongly demonstrated in **Spain**, where comprehensive assessor training, e-learning platforms²⁰, and tailored tools have been developed to support the transition from EPC to SRI assessments. The focus on large buildings aligned with the ≥ 290 kW threshold further supports testing at scale.

Stakeholder ecosystem engagement and market readiness

Engagement of engineering firms, research organisations²¹, and data platform providers enables practical learning and supports market preparedness²². This driver is evident in **Belgium Flanders** (*primarily non-residential*), where a broad ecosystem of technical actors participates in the pilot phase,

¹⁷ led by the Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik (OIB) in collaboration with the Federal Ministry for Climate Action (BMK), AEE INTEC, and BOKU Vienna; running since September 2021

¹⁸ https://srienact.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Module-2_2_Test-phase_Austria.pdf

¹⁹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator/sri-eu-countries_en

²⁰ <https://learning.sri2market.eu/moodle/>

²¹ such as EnergyVille(VITO, KU Leuven, imec, UHasselt) and Vito

²² In parallel, the Flemish transposition of the EPBD BACS obligation provides legal certainty and demand-side signals, reinforcing market readiness for smart readiness assessment tools such as SRI.

contributing implementation experience that is expected to inform a wider roll-out from 2025 onwards.

Clear reporting timelines and policy anchoring

Defined timelines for reporting test phase results strengthen policy signalling and implementation momentum. **Spain** and **Austria** being part of the official EU test phase demonstrates this driver through a clear commitment to report pilot outcomes to the European Commission by June 2026, with further technical modalities and a complementary act foreseen by June 2027.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Limited perceived benefits for building owners

A major barrier to SRI uptake is the absence of clear, tangible benefits for building owners, resulting in weak demand-side pull. This barrier has been identified as a reason for little interest and uptake in **Germany**, where the lack of incentives or perceived value for owners is identified as the main reason for the absence of an implementation driver, despite strong technical and research capacity.

In some national contexts, potential financial incentives linked to building flexibility remain uncertain or insufficiently stable to support investment decisions. For example, in Germany, reduced grid fees under §19(2) of the *Netzentgeltverordnung (NEV)* may be granted for atypical grid usage, which could in principle incentivise flexibility measures such as load shifting or battery storage. However, the relevant time windows for qualifying atypical consumption are redefined on an annual basis, limiting planning certainty for building owners. This regulatory uncertainty weakens the business case for investments in smart and flexible technologies and reduces the perceived benefits of engaging with instruments such as the SRI.

Uncertainty regarding the future regulatory role of the SRI

Where the long-term use of SRI results remains unclear, test phases tend to remain exploratory rather than deployment-oriented. This barrier is implicitly present in **Austria** and **Germany**, where pilots focus on methodological testing and infrastructure development without explicit indication of how SRI outcomes will be integrated into regulatory requirements, investment decisions, or existing certification schemes.

Potential overlap with existing national assessment frameworks

In countries with established national flexibility or energy performance assessment methods, the SRI may risk being perceived as duplicative if alignment is not clearly demonstrated. This barrier is implicitly suggested in **Austria**, where benchmarking against national methods is necessary to manage coexistence, highlighting the importance of careful integration. A similar concern emerges in **Germany**, where the Buildings Energy Act (GEG) already requires large non-residential buildings to be equipped with building automation and control systems in line with national standards (e.g. DIN V 18599 and EN 15232/ISO 52120). In this context, stakeholders may perceive the SRI as overlapping with existing compliance obligations unless its added value as a comparative and future-oriented smart readiness rating is clearly articulated.

Good practice

Spain illustrates good practice by combining methodological testing with strong operational readiness measures, including structured assessor training, digital tools, clear building scope, and defined reporting timelines to the European Commission.

Belgium (Flanders) demonstrates good practice in stakeholder engagement by involving a broad technical ecosystem early in the pilot phase, thereby strengthening market preparedness and implementation capacity.

Austria shows good practice in methodological integration by explicitly benchmarking the SRI against national flexibility frameworks, supporting coherence and policy learning.

Policy recommendations

Based on the country descriptions, several drivers critical for large-scale Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) uptake are not documented or remain insufficiently addressed and may require further attention by Member States:

- **Financial or regulatory incentives for building owners**, such as explicit links to funding schemes, regulatory relief, flexibility remuneration, or other market advantages
- **Strengthened legal certainty through timely and clear transposition**, including clarity on whether, when and how the SRI will be integrated into national regulatory frameworks, under which conditions it will remain voluntary, and for which building segments
- **Clear integration of SRI results into investment decision-making**, asset valuation, renovation planning, or portfolio management processes
- **Explicit links between the SRI and other EPBD instruments**, such as Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), building renovation passports, and digital building logbooks
- **Assessment and reduction of administrative and transaction costs**, including interoperability and data-access measures to reduce assessment burden and improve scalability
- **Translation of SRI scores into operational and economic value**, demonstrated through evidence on operational savings, flexibility revenues, improved comfort, or asset value enhancement

Clarify and communicate the value proposition of the SRI

To avoid perceptions of duplication with existing national requirements and assessment frameworks, it is essential to clearly articulate the added value of the Smart Readiness Indicator beyond regulatory compliance.

First, the SRI is an instrument that enables **value assessment of buildings**, supporting buying, selling and financing decisions by making the level of smart readiness, flexibility and future-proofing more transparent for market actors such as building owners, investors and financial institutions, where buildings are increasingly used as collateral or long-term assets.

Second, the role of SRI as a **structured and comparable assessment framework** was identified by practitioners, as it brings a single coherent structure for comparing diverse technical and functional aspects of buildings useful for deciding among suggested design options. By doing so, it can support decision-makers in comparing different combinations of renovation measures and system choices (e.g. envelope measures, HVAC upgrades, photovoltaics, storage and control systems), facilitating more informed and strategic investment decisions across multiple design and retrofit options.

IV.2. Zero-emission buildings

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Article 2 Definitions</i></p>	<p>Zero-emission building</p> <p>A building with a very high energy performance, as determined in accordance with Annex I, requiring zero or a very low amount of energy, producing zero on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels and producing zero or a very low amount of operational greenhouse gas emissions, in accordance with Article 11.</p>
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<i>Article 11 Zero-emission buildings</i>	<p>Member States shall ensure that the total annual primary energy use of a new or renovated zero-emission building is covered by:</p> <p>(a) energy from renewable sources generated on-site or nearby, fulfilling the criteria laid down in Article 7 of Directive (EU) 2018/2001;</p> <p>(b) energy from renewable sources provided from a renewable energy community within the meaning of Article 22 of Directive (EU) 2018/2001;</p> <p>(c) energy from an efficient district heating and cooling system in accordance with Article 26(1) of Directive (EU) 2023/1791; or</p> <p>(d) energy from carbon-free sources.</p>
<i>Article 2 Definitions</i>	(54) 'on-site' means in or on a particular building or on the land on which that building is located;
<i>Article 2 Definitions</i>	<p>(55) 'energy from renewable sources produced nearby' means energy from renewable sources, produced within a local or district-level perimeter of a particular building, which fulfils all of the following conditions:</p> <p>(a) it can be distributed and used only within that local and district-level perimeter through a dedicated distribution network;</p> <p>(b) it allows for the calculation of a specific primary energy factor valid only for the energy from renewable sources produced within that local or district-level perimeter; and</p> <p>(c) it can be used on-site through a dedicated connection to the energy production source, where that dedicated connection requires specific equipment for the safe supply and metering of energy for self-use of the building;</p>
<i>Recitals</i>	(23) Zero-emission buildings can contribute to demand-side flexibility for instance through demand management, electrical storage, thermal storage and distributed renewable generation to support a more reliable, sustainable and efficient energy system.

National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

National and regional methodologies for Zero-Emission Buildings (ZEB) are currently under development, as the deadline for transposing the revised EPBD is 29 May 2026. ZEB will replace the current Nearly Zero-Energy Building (NZEB) standard as the minimum energy performance requirement for new buildings, applying to

- new public buildings from 1 January 2028 and
- to all new buildings from 1 January 2030.

Compared to NZEB, the ZEB concept allows a broader use of renewable energy sources beyond on-site generation, including renewable energy produced nearby or through RECs. This creates synergies with

REDIII and can facilitate the implementation of CSC schemes, strengthening the role of buildings as active participants in the energy system.

Recital (23) highlights the contribution of ZEB to demand-side flexibility through demand management, electrical and thermal storage, and distributed renewable energy generation. In line with this, **Austria** explicitly recognises **energy storage as a supporting element for on-site renewable energy source** within its ZEB framework, thereby reinforcing the role of buildings as flexible energy assets.

In practice, **Austrian** ZEB concepts increasingly integrate smart building management systems, controllable loads, and electrical or thermal storage, enabling load shifting and responsiveness to external signals.

Regarding the treatment of *nearby* renewable energy sources in ZEB calculations, Austria applies a restrictive and technically robust interpretation. Nearby renewable energy may be included in the ZEB energy balance only if all of the following conditions are met:

1. **Energy Attribution:** Renewable energy must be directly measurable and uniquely attributable to the individual building (e.g. metered district heating from renewable sources or shared ground loops).
2. **Balance Boundary:** Renewable energy systems must lie within the defined energy balance boundary of the ZEB methodology.
3. **Monitoring and Metering:** Energy flows from nearby renewable energy must be monitored and metered in a manner equivalent to on-site generation, covering both delivered and exported energy.
4. **No Double Counting:** Renewable energy contributions must be fully traceable and cannot be claimed simultaneously by multiple buildings.²³

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https://nachhaltigwirtschaften.at/resources/iea_pdf/endbericht_201417_iea_shc_task40_ebc_annex_52_a_nhang03.pdf

Good practices

In Europe, a non-pilot country, **France**, provides one of the most comprehensive current national frameworks moving in the direction of zero-emission buildings, because RE2020 combines **operational energy performance, life-cycle carbon** and **summer comfort** within one regulatory approach. Several elements of this broader logic are also visible in the pilot countries, but usually in a more partial or fragmented way.

- **Germany**: strong on the **smart systems / automation** side, since the GEG requires large non-residential buildings to use building automation and digital energy monitoring.
- **Spain**: **renewables integration in building regulation**, especially the long-standing role of solar requirements in the Technical Building Code
- **Wallonia** and **Brussels** have clearly taken up the **building automation and control systems** dimension in EPB/PEB rules for non-residential buildings

Austria recognises battery storage as a supporting technology for on-site renewable energy. That matters for **design choices, valuation, compliance, and financing**, because the battery is no longer treated as an unrelated add-on but as part of a system that improves **self-consumption, reduced grid imports, and better matching of generation and demand**, i.e. improving the effective use of locally generated renewable electricity.

Nearby renewable energy (Austria)

- **Renewable Energy Communities (REC)**
Shared PV systems within neighbourhoods or buildings (legal under Austria's EAG)
→ Electricity can be distributed locally among participants via smart meters.
- District Heating and Cooling (DHC) from renewable sources:
Vienna's Fernwärme Wien increasingly uses biomass, waste heat, and large-scale solar thermal.
ZEBs can connect to DHC if it is partially or fully renewable.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Across all Member States, the detailed ZEB methodology under the revised EPBD is not yet fully defined. In particular, key elements such as the precise definition and accounting of *on-site* and *nearby* renewable energy sources remain pending, as the EPBD transposition deadline is set for May 2026. As a result, national approaches are still evolving, and regulatory certainty on ZEB energy balance boundaries is limited.

Policy recommendations

A timely and ambitious implementation of the ZEB methodology, aligned with updated cost-optimal levels, is essential to ensure regulatory coherence and investment certainty. While additional renewable energy sources, such as nearby generation and RECs, enable energy sharing and aggregation. Local optimisation and system flexibility require a clear prioritisation of on-site and nearby renewable energy over more distant sources. This hierarchy supports local renewable production, maximises grid-level benefits, and helps avoid costly grid upgrades.

The approach adopted in **Austria** anticipates future EPBD implementation by emphasising transparency, traceability, and system integrity, while minimising the risks of double counting and overestimation of ZEB performance.

IV.3. EV pre-cabling and ducting

EU-level provisions

<p><i>Recitals</i></p>	<p>(50) Combined with an increased share of renewable electricity production, electric vehicles produce less greenhouse gas emissions. Electric vehicles constitute an important component of a clean energy transition on the basis of energy efficiency measures, alternative fuels, renewable energy and innovative solutions for the management of energy flexibility. Building codes can be effectively used to introduce targeted requirements to support the deployment of recharging infrastructure in car parks of residential and non-residential buildings.</p>
<p><i>Recitals</i></p>	<p>(51) Pre-cabling and ducting facilitate the rapid deployment of recharging points if and where they are needed. Readily available infrastructure will decrease the costs of installation of recharging points for individual owners and ensure that electric vehicle users have access to recharging points. Establishing requirements for electromobility at Union level concerning the pre-equipping of parking spaces and the installation of recharging points is an effective way to promote electric vehicles in the near future while enabling further development at a reduced cost in the medium to long term. Where technically feasible, Member States should ensure the accessibility of recharging points for persons with disabilities.</p>
<p>Article 14 <i>Infrastructure for sustainable mobility</i></p>	<p>4. With regard to new residential buildings with more than three car parking spaces and residential buildings undergoing major renovation with more than three car parking spaces, Member States shall ensure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the installation of pre-cabling for at least 50% of car parking spaces and ducting, namely conduits for electric cables, for the remaining car parking spaces to enable the installation, at a later stage, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> of recharging points for electric vehicles, electrically power-assisted cycles and other L-category vehicle types; (aa) the installation of at least one recharging point for new residential buildings, and (b) at least two bicycle parking

National implementation

Key Drivers Enabling Buildings to Provide Energy Flexibility

In **Wallonia**, the EPBD requirements on infrastructure for sustainable mobility have been transposed by the Decree of 28 September 2023²⁴. The decree mandates EV pre-cabling in new buildings and buildings undergoing major renovation, requiring the installation of ducts and electrical capacity to

²⁴ <https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/loi-decret/2023/09/28/2023205617>

enable the future deployment of charging points in car parks. For non-residential buildings, minimum levels of pre-equipped parking spaces and the installation of recharging points are required, in line with Article 14 EPBD, ensuring EV readiness while limiting future retrofit costs.

Spain has implemented Article 14 EPBD through the CTE (Royal Decree 314/2006, as amended by Royal Decree 450/2022), notably in DB-HE Section HE 6²⁵. Pre-cabling for EV charging is mandatory in new buildings and major renovations, with 100% of parking spaces pre-equipped in new private residential buildings and 20% in buildings with other uses. In addition, non-residential buildings must install at least one charging point per 40 parking spaces, with stricter requirements applying to public buildings and accessible parking areas.

In **Poland**, EV readiness under the EPBD is mainly ensured through technical and electrical installation requirements rather than an explicit pre-cabling obligation. New buildings and renovations must provide sufficient connection capacity, cable routing infrastructure and protective systems to enable the installation of charging points, in compliance with applicable technical standards²⁶. These provisions effectively ensure that parking areas are prepared for EV charging in line with Article 14 EPBD objectives.

In **Austria**, the implementation of EPBD electromobility provisions is decentralised and implemented through the building regulations of the Länder (federal states), with OIB Guideline 6²⁷ providing a harmonising framework; for example, both Niederösterreich²⁸ and Tirol²⁹ explicitly include requirements for charging points and/or pre-cabling (Leitungsinfrastruktur) in their building rules.

Policy recommendations

The EPBD provisions on **EV pre-cabling and recharging infrastructure** are important for flexibility because they enable the large-scale integration of electric vehicles as flexible electricity loads within the power system and built environment. By requiring pre-cabling and ducting in new buildings and major renovations, the EPBD removes structural barriers to the deployment of smart and bidirectional charging infrastructure, which is a prerequisite for demand response, load shifting and, where applicable, EV-to-grid services.

Readily available charging infrastructure in residential and non-residential buildings allows EV charging to be aligned with periods of high renewable electricity generation and low system prices, thereby supporting the integration of variable renewables and reducing peak demand. **Embedding these requirements in building codes ensures that EV flexibility can be activated at low marginal cost over the lifetime of buildings, avoiding lock-in effects and costly retrofits.** As a result, EPBD electromobility provisions transform buildings and parked EVs into system-integrated flexibility assets, contributing to a more efficient, decarbonised and resilient energy system.

²⁵ [Código Técnico de la Edificación \(CTE\) Documento Básico \(DB\) de Ahorro de Energía \(HE\)](#)

²⁶ <https://greenkick.com.pl/blog/czy-stacja-ladowania-przy-domu-jednorodzinym-wymaga-pozwolenia-wyjasniamy-co-mowi-art-29a-prawa-budowlanego.and>
<https://plugbox.eu/blog/2025/03/04/udt-dla-stacji-ladowania/>

²⁷ <https://www.oib.or.at/kernaufgaben/oib-richtlinien/richtlinien/oib-richtlinien-2023/>

²⁸ <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/geltendefassung.wxe?abfrage=lrno&gesetzesnummer=20001079>

²⁹ <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/Landesnormen/LTI40043793/LTI40043793.html>

V. ENERGY EFFICIENCY DIRECTIVE

The revision of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), [Directive \(EU\) 2023/1791](#), raises the EU's energy-efficiency ambition and makes the targets legally binding. It requires a 11.7% reduction in final energy consumption by 2030 compared with the baseline projections.

V.1. Flexibility as part of Energy Efficiency First principle

EU-level provisions

<p>Article 3</p> <p>Directive (EU) 2023/1791</p>	<p>Energy Efficiency First principle</p> <p>In accordance with the energy efficiency first principle, Member States shall ensure that energy efficiency solutions, including demand-side resources and system flexibilities, are assessed in planning, policy and major investment decisions of a value of more than EUR 100,000,000 each or EUR 175,000,000 for transport infrastructure projects, relating to the following sectors:</p> <p>(a) energy systems; and</p> <p>(b) non-energy sectors, where those sectors have an impact on energy consumption and energy efficiency such as buildings, transport, water, information and communications technology (ICT), agriculture and financial sectors.</p>
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National implementation

Key drivers and emerging practices partially enabling buildings to provide energy flexibility

These drivers represent enabling conditions or pilot practices, but do not yet amount to systematic compliance with EED provisions.

Legal requirement to base network planning on demand evolution (demand forecasts).

Where the law requires development/adaptation plans to estimate future capacity needs using assumptions about future consumption/demand, this creates a direct entry point for assessing energy efficiency and demand-side effects. This driver is clearly present in

- **Austria** (NEP assumptions must cover development of “Verbrauch”),
- **Poland** (development plans to meet “current and future demand”), and
- **BE-Wallonia** (plan must consider probable evolution of “consommation”).

Explicit obligation to consider smart network management / flexibility (DSM-type measures) in grid planning to avoid reinforcement.

If the legal plan content requires the DSO to consider smart management, flexibility and flexible access as measures to meet needs (including avoiding grid reinforcement), that is a strong “EE1st in practice” driver. This is explicit in

- **Wallonia**: the plan content must take account of “gestion intelligente”, “flexibilité” and “accès flexibles” to help avoid reinforcement. It is also present in
- **Brussels**, where the plan requirements and regulator framing explicitly include assessing whether “services de flexibilité” could be an alternative to investments.

Regulator approval and procedural governance (consultation) for planning inputs.

EE1st-type assessment becomes more enforceable when planning inputs (e.g., scenario frameworks) are **formally approved** by the regulator and therefore cannot be ignored in the investment/planning chain. This is the core structural driver in

- **Germany**, where BNetzA approval of the **Szenariorahmen** is explicitly described as the foundation for the NEP planning.
- Austria has a parallel logic in the legal NEP duty with regulator oversight and explicit assumptions about demand evolution, but without the same explicit “DSM must be included” hook in the NEP clause itself.

Flexibility mechanisms explicitly embedded in electricity transmission planning to adapt to demand evolution.

A direct legal mention that transmission development planning must include “criteria and mechanisms of flexibility” to adapt to the real evolution of electricity demand provides a clear EE1st-aligned entry point. This is visible in

- **Spain’s electricity sector law** text on transmission development plans, which explicitly mentions “mecanismos de flexibilidad... para adaptarse a la evolución real de la demanda.”

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Planning laws often include demand evolution, but do not explicitly require DSM / demand response to be assessed as an alternative.

This creates “EE-only” planning rather than “EE + flexibility” planning. In **Austria**, the NEP legal clause requires assumptions on consumption development, but does not (in the clause retrieved) require DSM/flexibility to be included or assessed as an alternative. In **Poland**, the planning obligation is explicitly about meeting current/future demand, but an explicit DSM-assessment requirement is not apparent in the planning provisions referenced here.

Legal hooks exist at DSO planning level, but are weaker for “major investment decisions across the energy system.”

Belgium’s **Brussels** and **Wallonia** provisions are strong for DSO/local planning (development/adaptation plans), including flexibility as investment alternatives; however, they do not automatically extend to all “major investment decisions” across generation, sector coupling, or broader energy-system strategy without additional cross-sector rules or explicit EE1st screening requirements.

Regulatory instability / cancellation of reform instruments undermines DSM integration.

Spain’s 2025 reform instrument (RDL 7/2025) introduced explicit aggregation/DR provisions, including “servicios de respuesta de demanda,” but it was subsequently reported as **derogated** (creating legal uncertainty for some of the DSM-related reforms). Even where transmission planning law now references flexibility mechanisms for adapting to demand evolution, reform volatility can slow operational implementation.

Federal/regional split can blur where the “real” planning obligation sits and who enforces DSM.

In Belgium, substantial grid planning happens at multiple levels (federal transmission vs regional distribution planning). This can make it harder to implement an EE1st-style “whole energy system” assessment consistently, even if regional DSOs have flexibility hooks in their plan requirements. (This barrier is structural rather than a single missing clause; it shows up in the way Brussels/Wallonia focus on regional plans.)

Good practice

Germany: “scenario framework approval → binding basis for network development planning,” with flexibility/DSM handled in scenario assumptions (good example). Germany’s process is the clearest “EE1st-ready” governance chain among the pilots: TSOs develop a scenario framework, BNetzA approves it, and the approved framework becomes the basis for NEP planning. This creates a practical pathway to incorporate (and audit) electrification and DSM/flex assumptions (e.g., heat pumps, load management) as part of the planning baseline.

Wallonia: adaptation plan must include both demand evolution and explicit flexibility measures to avoid reinforcement.

Wallonia’s decree is explicit: the plan must include capacity needs assumptions accounting for probable consumption evolution, and it must consider smart management, flexibility, and flexible access as measures in planning. This is a strong legal model for embedding “efficiency + flexibility” into grid investment logic.

Brussels: development plan requirements framed to test flexibility services as an alternative to grid investments. Brussels’ development plan framework (as articulated by BRUGEL when referencing the legal base) includes assessing whether alternatives to investments—such as flexibility services—are possible. That is directly aligned with the EED requirement to “assess demand-side resources and flexibilities” in planning and investment decisions. Spain illustrates good practice by combining methodological testing with strong operational readiness measures, including structured assessor training, digital tools, clear building scope, and defined reporting timelines to the European Commission.

Belgium (Flanders) demonstrates good practice in stakeholder engagement by involving a broad technical ecosystem early in the pilot phase, thereby strengthening market preparedness and implementation capacity.

Austria shows good practice in methodological integration by explicitly benchmarking the SRI against national flexibility frameworks, supporting coherence and policy learning.

Policy recommendations

- Provision of definitions for flexible and efficient operation of the energy systems.
- Development of methodologies to assess the needed flexibility to achieve quantified energy efficiency targets
- Promote the adoption of sector-coupling technologies
- Promote the adoption of dynamic energy tariff

V.2. Role of energy communities within heating and cooling plans

This analysis examines the implementation of EU Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) Article 25.6(da), which requires Member States to assess the role of energy communities in local heating and cooling plans for municipalities with over 45,000 inhabitants. The study compares legislation and frameworks across Poland, Spain, Austria, Germany, and Belgium (Wallonia and Brussels) to identify key drivers, barriers, and good practices facilitating energy community participation.

EU-level provisions

<p>Article 25</p> <p>Directive (EU) 2023/1791</p>	<p>Heating and cooling assessment and planning</p> <p>Member States shall ensure that regional and local authorities prepare local heating and cooling plans at least in municipalities having a total population higher than 45,000.</p> <p>(da) assess the role of energy communities and other consumer-led initiatives that can actively contribute to the implementation of local heating and cooling projects</p>
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National implementation

Key drivers and emerging practices partially enabling buildings to provide energy flexibility

These drivers represent enabling conditions or pilot practices, but do not yet amount to systematic compliance with EED provisions.

Established Legal Framework for Energy Communities

A clear legal definition and regulatory framework for renewable energy communities (RECs) and citizen energy communities (CECs) significantly enables their participation in heating and cooling planning.

Austria has established the most comprehensive legal framework with the Renewable Energy Act (Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz, EAG) passed in July 2021. This act provides clear definitions for RECs and CECs and established a federal Coordination Office for Energy Communities (COEC) that supports implementation and maps existing initiatives. Austria recognizes multiple forms: RECs, CECs, Community Generation Plants, and Energy Cooperatives.

Germany incorporated energy community provisions into the Renewable Energy Sources Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz, EEG), defining "citizen energy companies" as the overarching term. The amended EEG (2023) includes stricter business limitations to prevent corporate capture and clarifies citizen ownership rights. Germany established a National Office for Energy Cooperatives to advocate and develop community projects.

Belgium (Wallonia) has legally recognised and operationalised renewable energy communities: established legal framework for renewable thermal energy communities that goes beyond district-heating development alone³⁰. The framework applies broadly to situations involving thermal energy consumption and grants renewable thermal energy communities rights including

³⁰ <https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/arrete/2022/07/07/2022033704/2022/10/22>; **Article 3, §3** "toutes les situations où de l'énergie thermique est consommée." apply for the **scope** of "Renewable thermal energy communities" and "Planning and preliminary studies for the development of a thermal energy network".

production, supply, self-consumption, sharing, aggregation, flexibility services, storage and the sale of surplus thermal energy.

Belgium (Brussels) recognizes energy communities through its Brussels Air, Climate and Energy Code (CoBrACE, amended in December 2020 and March 2024). The region supports specific energy cooperative models and provides municipal energy expert positions.

Poland has not fully transposed EU provisions on RECs and CECs into national law, and there is no clear legal definition of energy communities. Energy cooperatives exist but operate under different legal structures without specific energy community designation. This represents a significant barrier rather than a driver.

Municipal Heating and Cooling Planning Obligations

Clear legal mandates for municipalities to develop heating and cooling plans create a structural requirement for integrating energy communities. A dedicated law mandating **municipal heat planning at scale** is a major accelerator, which provides the institutional setting where the EED’s “assess energy communities’ role” can be mainstreamed via guidance/templates.

This is clearly present in **Germany** through the **Wärmeplanungsgesetz (WPG)**. Germany has made municipal heat planning mandatory for all municipalities since 2024, with specific timelines based on population size. The Local Heat Planning Act (WPG) requires a three-step approach: inventory analysis, renewable energy potential assessment, and scenario development. This creates a formal opportunity for energy communities to assess their role in future heat supply.

Austria (federal government working with Länder (federal states) is developing a national heating and cooling strategy aiming for full heat decarbonisation by 2040. While not yet fully in law, this policy direction supports energy community involvement in planning.

Belgium (Wallonia) has institutional integration into planning: it mandates district heating opportunity studies which could be expanded (see barriers).³⁰ In detail, Wallonia provides a partial planning driver by requiring opportunity studies for renewable- or waste-heat-based thermal energy networks in municipal planning and selected development projects. This creates a concrete institutional entry point for collective thermal solutions and can support the consideration of community-led heat initiatives in local planning.

Belgium (Brussels) is developing a robust framework that maps renewable heat potentials by district and requires energy planning at the municipal level, creating entry points for energy community participation.

Poland requires energy supply plans under Article 19 of the Energy Law, which requires the mayor to prepare “assumptions” for a municipal supply plan for **heat, electricity and gas**, and the plan must include an assessment of current and forecast demand for heat, etc. These plans are generally carried out in isolation from climate and spatial planning, and compliance rates are low. No specific mandate exists for heating and cooling planning as required by EED Article 25.6.

Spain has no legal requirement for municipalities to prepare local heating and cooling plans. Some autonomous communities are developing regional strategies, but these are not mandatory, and local authorities lack strong obligations to incorporate energy communities.

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Weak or Fragmented Legal Frameworks for Energy Communities

Summary: Absence of clear legal definitions or incomplete transposition of EU energy community provisions prevents communities from operating effectively in heating and cooling sectors.

Poland has not fully transposed EU provisions on renewable energy communities and citizen energy communities into national law. There is no clear legal definition distinguishing energy communities from energy cooperatives. Only a few energy cooperatives operate, primarily as small-scale initiatives. This legal uncertainty makes it difficult for communities to organize around heating and cooling projects and limits their formal role in municipal planning.

Spain has not yet fully transposed Article 25 of Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on local planning for heating and cooling, including the assessment of the role of energy communities and other consumer-led initiatives.

Austria faces coordination challenges across nine Länder (federal states) with different regional frameworks, creating fragmentation in energy community support and opportunities, though a national framework exists.

Limited Attention to Energy Communities' Heating and Cooling Role in Policy

Energy community provisions in heating and cooling planning remain underdeveloped or absent from national and regional policy frameworks, despite EU requirements.

Poland has not yet integrated energy communities into heating transition discussions at the national level. The focus on energy planning remains narrow, and explicit mention of energy community roles in heating is absent from policy documents.

Spain lacks any specific policy emphasis on energy communities' roles in local heating and cooling planning. The national focus remains on renewable electricity rather than heating and cooling decarbonization.

Austria (federal government) is developing a heating strategy but has not explicitly prioritized energy communities' roles within this strategy, though opportunities exist for integration.

Germany addresses energy communities in the Local Heat Planning Act but does not provide specific mechanisms for mandatory energy community assessment, leaving their role somewhat implicit rather than explicit.

Belgium (Wallonia): Wallonia's framework for renewable thermal energy communities is broader than district-heating development alone. However, the associated planning instruments remain more narrowly focused: Articles 110 and 111 of the order³¹ require 'opportunity studies' on the deployment of renewable- or waste-heat-based thermal energy networks in municipal planning and selected development projects. This creates a concrete entry point for collective network solutions, but does not yet amount to a systematic assessment of the full range of community-led heating and cooling options.

Lack of Coordination with Spatial Planning and Building Regulations

Disconnect between energy planning and spatial/urban planning frameworks prevents integrated design of heating systems that leverage energy community potential.

Poland heat planning is not well integrated into local spatial planning and governance practices. Coordination between energy supply planning and municipal zoning/building codes is weak.

Spain and other southern/eastern European countries experience a gap between energy planning (traditionally focused on supply security) and spatial planning that reflects urban development priorities. In Spain, the policy discussion is beginning to reflect both heating and cooling needs, including the growing need for cooling in residential buildings. However, the emerging regulatory approach remains focused mainly on efficient heating and cooling networks and does not yet explicitly integrate the role of energy communities and other consumer-led initiatives in local heating and cooling planning.

Austria and **Germany** are working to bridge this gap through municipal heat planning incorporating spatial analysis, but this integration remains incomplete in many jurisdictions.

³¹ <https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/arrete/2022/07/07/2022033704/2022/10/22>; Article 3, §3 "toutes les situations où de l'énergie thermique est consommée." apply for the scope of "Renewable thermal energy communities" and "Planning and preliminary studies for the development of a thermal energy network".

Missing or Inadequate Cooling Planning

Cooling demand is growing, particularly in southern Europe, yet cooling is systematically overlooked in municipal heating and cooling plans and energy community frameworks.

All countries studied show limited attention to cooling planning relative to heating. No country has developed comprehensive national support frameworks specifically for cooling planning. Southern regions with growing cooling needs face particular challenges as existing frameworks focus primarily on heating solutions. For example, in Spain, where policy documents already point to a growing need for cooling in residential buildings, the future transposition of Article 25 of Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on local heating and cooling planning will need to ensure adequate attention not only to heating solutions but also to cooling needs and related consumer-led options.

Good practice

Good Practice for Comprehensive Legal Framework with Clear Definitions:
Austria's Energy Community Act (EAG 2021)

Austria established the most comprehensive legal framework recognizing multiple energy community forms: Renewable Energy Communities, Citizen Energy Communities, Community Generation Plants, and Energy Cooperatives. The Renewable Energy Act provides clear definitions, legal rights, and operational procedures. A federal Coordination Office for Energy Communities (COEC) was established to support implementation and maintain registries.

Implementation Elements:

- Clear legal definitions distinguishing types of energy communities
- Established coordination structures at national level
- Support for diverse organizational models (cooperatives, associations, etc.)
- Official registry and mapping of existing communities

Transferability: Poland, Spain, and Belgium (Wallonia) could adopt similar clarity in legal frameworks. Poland particularly needs explicit energy community definitions in national energy law.

Documentation: Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz (EAG),
<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abkürzung=EAG%202021>

Good practice (continued)

**Mandatory Municipal Heat Planning with Energy Community Assessment:
Germany's Local Heat Planning Act (WPG) and Building Energy Act (GEG)**

Germany made municipal heat planning mandatory for all municipalities starting in 2024, with the Local Heat Planning Act (WPG) requiring a three-step approach: (1) inventory analysis identifying existing heating networks and heat sources; (2) renewable energy potential assessment (biogas, solar thermal, geothermal, waste heat); and (3) scenario development addressing climate objectives and affordability. The act specifically requires assessment of renewable sources and district heating potential, creating a structured opportunity for energy community participation.

Implementation Elements:

- Mandatory heat planning timelines for all municipalities >45,000 inhabitants
- Three-step methodological approach ensuring comprehensive data collection
- Explicit identification of renewable energy and waste heat potential
- Open-access data requirements from energy utilities
- Timeline targets: 30% renewable/waste heat in existing networks by 2030, 80% by 2040, 100% by 2045

Transferability: Poland and Spain particularly need such mandatory frameworks. Austria is developing a national heating strategy; this could be formalized into binding legal requirements.

Documentation: Wärmeplanungsgesetz (WPG), <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/wpg/>

Policy recommendations

The analysis reveals that successful implementation of EED Article 25.6(da) requires a coordinated, multi-level approach combining legal clarity, institutional support, technical capacity, and financial resources. Across all six countries studied, priority areas emerge:

Establishing or strengthening legal frameworks that explicitly recognize and define energy communities in the heating and cooling context.³²

Creating binding municipal heat planning obligations with mandatory energy community assessment mechanisms.

The critical insight is that energy communities' potential to contribute to local heating decarbonization remains substantially underutilized across all countries, not due to technical barriers but due to insufficient legal clarity, institutional support, and explicit policy recognition of their role.

³² Current EU and national definitions of energy communities emerged primarily from the renewable electricity sector, focusing on generation, distribution, and supply of electricity. However, the heating and cooling sector presents fundamentally different technical, economic, and organizational characteristics that require explicit adaptation of energy community definitions and operational frameworks.

Key Message:

The critical insight is that energy communities' potential to contribute to local heating decarbonization remains substantially underutilized across all countries, not due to technical barriers but due to insufficient legal clarity, institutional support, and explicit policy recognition of their role. While all pilot countries have introduced legal frameworks enabling energy communities, none yet explicitly require their systematic assessment within local heating and cooling plans, revealing a consistent transposition gap with Article 25 of the Energy Efficiency Directive.

V.3. DSOs should consider flexibility

EU-level provisions

<p>Article 27 Directive (EU) 2023/1791</p>	<p>Energy transformation, transmission and distribution</p> <p>National regulatory authorities or other designated national authorities shall verify that methodologies used by transmission system operators and distribution system operators assess alternatives in the cost-benefit analysis and take into account the wider benefits of energy efficiency solutions, demand-side flexibility and investment into assets that contribute to climate change mitigation.</p>
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National implementation

Key drivers and emerging practices partially enabling buildings to provide energy flexibility

These drivers represent enabling conditions or pilot practices, but do not yet amount to systematic compliance with Article 27.

DSO-Aggregator Collaboration Framework (Poland, Spain)

Poland and **Spain** have established regulatory frameworks enabling direct contracts between DSOs and flexibility providers or aggregators controlling efficient and flexible devices. In **Poland**, regulatory changes implemented in June 2024 introduced new balancing market rules requiring dispatch units to participate in the balancing market and submit work programmes to the TSO. The Polish Energy Regulatory Office (URE) published the 2024 Report on Redispatching Mechanisms, documenting DSO flexibility procurement procedures. This framework provides legal certainty for aggregators and flexibility service providers to engage in demand-side flexibility markets. **Spain** has now formally approved a regulatory framework for independent aggregation through Real Decreto 88/2026³³. Consumers may contract aggregation services in parallel to their electricity supply contract without requiring the supplier's consent, and independent aggregators are granted the right to participate in

³³ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2026-3212>

electricity markets, including balancing services, subject to the relevant technical and operational rules. The regulation provides that the **system operator** and, where relevant, the **market operator** will play central roles in implementation and settlement arrangements; in Spain, these functions are performed by **Red Eléctrica (REE)** and **OMIE**, respectively, with operating procedures and data-exchange formats to be implemented within two to three months. While these implementing procedures are still being adapted, the legal framework itself is now in place.

Germany provides an additional and particularly relevant example through § 14c EnWG³⁴. The provision gives DSOs a clear legal basis to procure flexibility services for the distribution network in a transparent, non-discriminatory and market-based procedure where this improves the efficiency of grid operation and grid expansion. Its intended added value is not only that flexibility is permitted in principle, but that procurement must be structured in a way that allows market participants to participate effectively, with specifications and suitable standardised market products subject to regulatory approval. This strengthens legal certainty, improves market access for aggregators and other flexibility providers, and supports the use of flexibility as an alternative or complement to conventional grid reinforcement.³⁵

Relevant legislation: Poland - Act on the Electricity Market and regulations by URE; Spain - Royal Decree and regulations by CNMC (National Commission of Markets and Competition); Germany - EnWG § 14 c Market-based procurement of flexibility services in the electricity distribution network

Grid Hosting Capacity and Transparent Capacity Planning (Austria, Germany, Belgium)

Austria, Germany, and Belgium have mandated that DSOs publish transparent information on available grid capacity at different voltage levels. Austria's implementation is particularly advanced, with requirements that grid connection procedures include clarity on hosting capacity calculations, particularly at low voltage levels where over 90% of PV installations are below 250 kW. Germany requires DSOs to provide quarterly updates on available capacity. Belgium (particularly Flanders) implements current best practice with clear timelines for grid connection procedures and transparent identification of reinforcement capacity and timeframes by substation. These frameworks enable flexibility providers to make informed decisions about participating in flexibility markets by understanding where grid constraints exist.

Relevant legislation: Austria - Electricity Act and E-Control regulations; Germany - Electricity Grid Connection Ordinance (StromNZV); Belgium (Flanders) - VREG regulations and distribution system regulations

Regulatory Support for Sector Coupling and Thermal Networks (Belgium - Wallonia)

Belgium's Walloon region has promoted the design of flexible and sector-coupled thermal networks as a flexibility solution. The framework enables DSOs to jointly plan electricity and heating network development by considering district heating and cooling as alternatives to grid reinforcement. The Walloon Commission for Energy (CWaPE) has developed methodologies allowing thermal network operators and DSOs to coordinate investments. This driver recognizes that demand-side flexibility in heating (through heat pumps, thermal storage, and demand response) can provide significant flexibility to electricity distribution grids.

Relevant legislation: Wallonia - Regional heating and cooling regulations; Ordonnance RENOLUTION (February 2024); Circular on district heating and cooling planning

Barriers to Unlocking the Flexibility Potential of Buildings

Lack of National Transposition and DSO Obligations in Heating Planning (Spain)

³⁴ https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/enwg_2005/_14c.html

³⁵ <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/19/274/1927453.pdf>

Spain faces significant barriers in coordinating DSO involvement with local energy efficiency and heating planning. It can be observed that Spain has expanded its active demand-response capability, with REE allocating 497 MW in the first auction for the period November 2022 to October 2023³⁶ and announcing 1,148 MW for 2025³⁷. However, while this shows growing use of demand-side flexibility in system operation, the regulatory framework still lacks specific requirements for DSOs to consider energy efficiency and demand-side flexibility as alternatives in their network development plans.

No mandatory methodologies exist to jointly evaluate local energy-efficient planning with local grid operation. The transposition of Article 32 of the Electricity Directive in Spain has occurred, but implementation remains focused on market-based solutions without equivalent regulatory obligations for DSOs to assess flexibility in heating and cooling contexts. Furthermore, aggregation of flexibility services faces legal barriers, with independent aggregators still unable to fully participate in network development planning alongside DSOs.

Relevant legislation: Spain - Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector (partially updated); draft amendments pending full EED transposition deadline (January 2025)

Insufficient Remuneration and Incentive Mechanisms for Flexibility (Poland, Germany)

A key barrier lies in how network regulation treats different types of expenditure. In simplified terms, **CAPEX** refers to investment in (capital expenditure on) physical grid assets such as cables, transformers, substations and digital control equipment, while **OPEX** refers to recurring operational expenditure such as procuring local flexibility services, activating demand response, or running congestion-management processes. Where tariff regulation provides clearer cost recovery and remuneration for CAPEX than for OPEX, **DSOs have a structural incentive to solve congestion through grid reinforcement rather than through local flexibility procurement**, even where flexibility could be more cost-effective.

In **Poland**, the regulatory framework³⁸ still appears more clearly geared towards investment-led network development. URE's guidance on priority investments explicitly provides for the recovery of justified costs and a justified return on capital for priority network tasks and investments. At the same time, URE's 'Karta Efektywnej Transformacji' shows that broader use of flexibility still depends on further roll-out of smart metering, SCADA, EMS/DMS, communications and settlement systems. This suggests that flexibility is recognised as important, but that the regulatory and operational framework still gives a clearer signal for infrastructure expansion than for routine procurement of local flexibility services.

In **Germany**, the situation is more dynamic and should be considered more carefully. Since 1 January 2024, the Bundesnetzagentur's framework under **§ 14a EnWG** has required the integration of controllable consumer devices such as heat pumps and private EV charge points and allows consumers, under one option, to coordinate reductions themselves via an energy management system.³⁹ However, the Bundesnetzagentur has also stated in the **AgNes** process that the **current** network tariff system still provides no incentives to reward flexible behaviour, but rather the opposite. The ongoing AgNes reform is therefore explicitly examining how tariff structures, including dynamic tariff components, can better reward flexibility; the 2025 orientation paper⁴⁰ notes that controllable

³⁶ <https://www.sistemaelectrico-ree.es/en/2022/spanish-electricity-system/markets/average-final-price>

³⁷ <https://www.ree.es/en/press-office/news/press-release/2024/11/the-peninsular-electricity-system-will-have-1148-mw-demand-side-response-capacity-2025>

³⁸ <https://www.ure.gov.pl/download/9/14821/WytycznePrezesaUREInwestycjePriorytetowe.pdf>,
<https://www.ure.gov.pl/download/9/14730/Zalacznik1.pdf>

³⁹ https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/EN/2023/20231127_14a.html;
https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/enwg_2005/_14c.html

⁴⁰

https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/EN/2025/20250512_AgNes.html ;

consumers under § 14a EnWG are in principle suitable for dynamic network tariffs. Germany therefore still faces a barrier, but increasingly a **transitional** one: technical controllability is being put in place, while the tariff framework needed to valorise that flexibility is still under reform.

An additional barrier is that DSOs are strongly responsible for secure and reliable network operation. Where continuity and quality of supply are closely monitored and linked to regulatory consequences, operators may be more risk-averse in practice and prefer conventional reinforcement over flexibility-based solutions unless the latter are clearly supported by the regulatory framework. In Poland, this logic is reinforced by quality regulation using SAIDI and SAIFI indicators. In Germany, the point should be framed more cautiously: the technical basis for controllability has recently been strengthened under § 14a EnWG, but tariff reform to reward flexible behaviour more systematically is still under discussion.

Relevant legislation: Poland - Energy Law; 2022 tariff ordinance; URE tariff calculation note 2025; URE WACC methodology 2023–2028.; Germany - EnWG §14a, Electricity Network Regulation (StromNEV) and Federal Network Agency (BNetzA) regulatory decisions, ARegV; BNetzA BK8-22/010-A; BNetzA AgNes.

Barriers to Direct DSO Involvement and Coordination (Belgium - Wallonia, Brussels)

Both the **Walloon** and **Brussels** regions face three main institutional barriers to effective coordination between electricity, gas, and thermal network planning. **First, the formal involvement of gas and electricity DSOs in local heating and cooling planning remains limited.** In Wallonia, while heating and cooling opportunity studies are mandatory for district systems, regulatory obligations for DSO (gas and electricity) participation in joint planning with thermal network developers or operators remain weak. Brussels has established a regional Taskforce including DSO representatives, but this does not yet ensure systematic coordination in practice as resource constraints (staffing shortages at municipal and regional levels) limit implementation capacity.

Second, joint planning is hindered by a lack of standardised methodologies, data, and technical support. In both regions, the absence of harmonised cost-benefit assessment methods to jointly evaluate electricity grid needs and thermal network development creates uncertainty for flexibility procurement and investments in future electricity infrastructure and possible gas network decommissioning. Data availability and technical support also remain uneven across municipalities, limiting coordinated planning and reducing thermal network developers' access to relevant system information, needed for decision-making.

Third, regulatory frameworks do not provide clear remuneration and cost-recovery mechanisms for coordination and the procurement of flexibility services, or for related enabling investments and coordination costs. As a result, DSOs face weak incentives to engage proactively in thermal network coordination or to support flexibility-based alternatives to conventional infrastructure development. Weak market access and remuneration for demand-side flexibility also limits the pool of resources that DSOs could rely on as alternatives to grid reinforcement: *The flexibility value of demand-side assets is often not sufficiently remunerated, weakening incentives for households and companies to invest in them.* Households and companies may invest in assets such as batteries, thermal storage, or smart control systems that can provide flexibility to the grid. However, the flexibility value of these assets is often not sufficiently remunerated through clear market access or stable incentive mechanisms, which weakens investment incentives. This also limits the development of local flexibility markets, because potential providers on the demand side lack a strong business case to make flexibility-enabling investments.

For Spain, available input also suggests that remuneration and incentive frameworks for DSO engagement in flexibility and efficiency-related coordination may not yet be sufficiently developed. However, the evidence provided does not specify the regulatory provisions in detail.

https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Beschlusskammern/1_GZ/GBK-GZ/2025/GBK-25-01-1x3_AgNes/GBK-25-01-1x3_Verfahrenseinleitung.html?nn=666514;

Relevant legislation: Wallonia - CWaPE regulations on heating and cooling planning; Brussels - RENOLUTION ordonnance and Brugel regulations; Belgium federal - CREG coordination frameworks

Policy recommendations

Develop and Standardize Cost-Benefit Analysis Methodologies for Flexibility Assessment

All six countries should establish clear, mandatory methodologies for TSOs and DSOs to conduct cost-benefit analyses comparing grid expansion with flexibility procurement, explicit demand-side efficiency measures, and sector-coupled solutions. These methodologies must incorporate the "wider benefits" of energy efficiency solutions as required by Article 27 of the EED, including benefits for energy security, system resilience, CO2 emission reduction, and consumer benefits. Cost-benefit analysis frameworks should be harmonized across regions to ensure consistency, transparency, and appropriate consideration of non-financial factors. NRAs should develop guidelines specifying which flexibility alternatives must be considered before approving infrastructure investments exceeding defined thresholds. Regulatory decisions on DSO investment plans should be conditional upon evidence of systematic flexibility assessment.

Implementation lead: National regulatory authorities (URE in Poland; CNMC in Spain; E-Control in Austria; BNetzA in Germany; VREG, CWaPE, Brugel in Belgium)

Establish Regulatory Incentives for DSO Flexibility Procurement

Poland and Germany urgently require regulatory reforms to incentivize DSO flexibility procurement. This should include: (1) tariff methodologies providing equivalent revenue certainty for flexibility-based solutions as for infrastructure expansion; (2) regulatory performance targets rewarding DSOs achieving network development objectives through flexibility; (3) mechanisms for DSOs to recover costs of flexibility procurement including transaction costs; (4) financial incentives through allowed return rates comparable to CAPEX investments. Spain should similarly strengthen incentive mechanisms. Belgium should develop region-specific incentive frameworks, ensuring Brussels and Wallonia can offer adequate remuneration for flexibility procurement. These mechanisms should be reviewed annually and adjusted based on market development and flexibility availability.

Member States and regulators should further develop regulatory and market frameworks that improve the visibility, accessibility, and remuneration of demand-side flexibility, including flexibility provided through batteries, thermal storage, and smart control systems. This would support the practical implementation of the requirement for DSOs to consider flexibility-based alternatives to conventional grid reinforcement.

Implementation lead: National regulatory authorities and regional regulators,

Co-leads / key implementers: the relevant ministry and the DSOs

Foster Systematic Collaboration Between DSOs, Flexibility Providers, and Thermal Network Operators

Poland and Spain should establish regulatory frameworks mandating formal coordination mechanisms between DSOs, aggregators, and flexibility service providers during network development planning. Specifically: (1) DSOs must publish annual flexibility needs assessments identifying local constraints and required flexibility services; (2) aggregators and flexibility providers have guaranteed access to submit solutions; (3) joint planning procedures are established for integrated electricity and heating network development where thermal solutions can address electricity constraints. Belgium (Wallonia and Brussels) should expand the existing regional Taskforces to include formal decision-making authority and dedicated funding for electricity/gas DSO-thermal network coordination studies. Austria and Germany should further strengthen structured coordination between DSOs, flexibility providers, and thermal network operators, building on existing transparency requirements. This could include more formalised procedures for information exchange,

joint planning, and the identification of flexibility-based alternatives during network development planning. All countries should develop standardized templates and data exchange procedures enabling efficient coordination.

Implementation lead: National regulatory authorities, in coordination with DSOs, aggregators, and local authorities

Key Message

The assessment shows that the main barrier to effective implementation of Article 27 of the Energy Efficiency Directive is not the absence of legal provisions, but structural features of national regulatory frameworks that systematically favour grid expansion over demand-side flexibility. Across all six countries analysed, CAPEX-biased incentive regulation, weak requirements for integrated electricity and heating/cooling planning, and fragmented transposition of EU rules prevent TSOs and DSOs from objectively assessing flexibility and energy efficiency as alternatives to infrastructure investment. Without targeted regulatory reform to address these incentive and coordination failures, Article 27 risks remaining a formal obligation rather than a driver of cost-effective system planning.

VI. KEY TAKEAWAYS

- Buildings can only become effective flexibility assets where the implementation of the EMD, RED III, EPBD and EED is coherent. Market access, renewable energy sharing, smart-readiness, data access and planning rules must work together; no single directive is sufficient on its own.
- Across the analysed countries, the regulatory foundations for energy sharing, aggregation and citizen participation are emerging, but implementation remains uneven and often incomplete, a delayed or restrictive national transposition and operationalisation, limiting the practical uptake of flexibility at building and neighbourhood level.
- Energy communities, collective self-consumption and aggregation can support building-level and neighbourhood-level flexibility, but their practical uptake is still limited by legal complexity, administrative burdens, restrictive proximity rules and insufficient clarity on the interaction between different frameworks.
- Several enabling practices already exist across the analysed countries, including clearer REC and CEC frameworks, broader possibilities for collective self-consumption, stronger data-access arrangements, and more advanced SRI testing and implementation support. However, these enabling elements are not yet combined systematically into coherent national frameworks.
- Data availability from DSOs remains a key bottleneck. Even where access rights exist, limited scope, delays, manual procedures or insufficient interoperability continue to restrict energy sharing, storage optimisation and flexibility services.
- The EPBD provides an important enabling layer through the Smart Readiness Indicator, zero-emission buildings and EV-ready infrastructure, but these provisions will only translate into system value where they are linked to incentives, digital infrastructure, skilled assessors and access to flexibility markets.
- Under the EED, flexibility and energy efficiency are still not systematically treated as alternatives to grid expansion in planning and investment decisions. CAPEX-biased incentives, weak coordination and insufficient integration of energy communities into local heating and cooling planning continue to limit progress.
- Overall, the report shows that regulatory readiness for smart grid-ready buildings depends on turning existing legal principles into workable, coordinated and low-transaction-cost frameworks that enable households, communities and service providers to participate effectively.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable shows that the role of buildings in the energy system is no longer limited to reducing consumption. Under the combined framework of the Electricity Market Design, Renewable Energy Directive, Energy Performance of Buildings Directive and Energy Efficiency Directive, buildings are increasingly expected to contribute to the energy transition not only through energy efficiency improvements, but also through energy sharing, aggregation, storage, smart control and participation in energy communities. Taken together, these directives shape whether buildings can act as flexible energy system assets at building and neighbourhood level and support the wider integration of renewables, electrification and system optimisation. However, these possibilities do not yet translate consistently into practical and scalable flexibility solutions at building and neighbourhood level.

Across the analysed demo locations, the assessment shows that enabling elements already exist, but their implementation remains fragmented. The analysis does not point to one single leading national model. Rather, some Member States provide more advanced examples for specific aspects, such as broader collective self-consumption and clearer pathways for multiple contracts in Spain, clearer REC and data-access arrangements in Austria, stakeholder engagement and aggregation-related governance in Belgium, and selected enabling elements in Germany and Poland in areas such as aggregation, heating and cooling planning or data infrastructure. At the same time, important barriers persist. Regulatory complexity, fragmented transposition, limited data access, administrative burdens, and insufficient alignment between market rules, community frameworks, smart-building provisions and planning obligations continue to constrain uptake in practice.

Overall, the key challenge is not only to introduce relevant legal provisions, but to ensure that they work together in practice. Unlocking the flexibility potential of buildings will require better alignment across directives and national implementation frameworks so that data access, market access, energy sharing, smart-building requirements and system planning function as mutually reinforcing elements. Only under these conditions can buildings support a more decarbonised, efficient, resilient and consumer-centred energy system by integrating distributed renewables, reducing system costs and grid pressure, and enabling citizens and communities to participate more actively in the energy transition.

